

COMPARISON OF DESIGN OF MULTI-RISERS USING STIFFNESS MATRIX METHOD AND CONTINUUM METHOD

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Master of Engineering
In
Civil Engineering
(With Structural Engineering Subjects)

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A
Dissertation Report On
**COMPARISON OF DESIGN OF MULTI-RISERS USING STIFFNESS MATRIX
METHOD AND CONTINUUM METHOD**

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Abstract

The most common Superstructure modelling procedure is the fixed base approach which assumes infinite stiffness at the foundation –soil interface. The above assumption is valid only for light structures on very stiff, rocky strata. It is seen that the relative stiffness between the superstructure & foundation is the major influencing factor. The current codes do not specify the provision of Soil-Structure-Interaction effects on the super structure modelling. Literature study showed a large number of case studies of the soil structure interaction effects on the low rise buildings. The S.S.I effect for the low rise buildings is considered to be more severe because of the height as it results in much smaller time period which generally falls in the linearly increasing range in the response spectrum given in IS 1893(Part 1).The linear range gives a higher value of the seismic base shear due to increased period on account of consideration of flexibility of soils. Also the earthquake forces are the predominant dynamic load case for low to medium rise buildings.

In the present study, the performance of a set of multi –risers with similar plan, geometric configuration and material properties with variable heights is checked considering the soil structure interaction model with respect to the fixed base model. The assessment of the variation in design due to the soil structure interaction effect is done. For the purpose, the study of various soil structure models was done and the pros and cons of each model were studied and a comparative assessment was done to find the best suitable model for the problem in consideration. The IS code specifications for the dynamic load case analysis of structures were studied to know the assumptions made for the dynamic analysis of structures and also select the best soil structure model. The most common dynamic load analysis methods for the R.C.C buildings are the equivalent lateral force method and the response spectrum method for the seismic forces and the wind load analysis is done using the static method of application of wind forces calculated from the wind pressure which is dependent on the basic wind speed. Hence the representation of soil medium as static springs whose stiffness values are calculated using a continuum method where the soil is viewed as a continuum with elastic properties and the solution involves rigid body motion equations and the matrix of dynamic influence is solved using various methods like Laplace's transformations, Fourier transformations etc. The paper "Analysis of Machine foundation vibrations" by George Gazetas has given the various soil models and the different

methodologies used in the solutions which was used as reference to compute the spring stiffnesses. The fixed base analysis was done and an appropriate foundation was arrived at. The direct method of the interaction study in which the soil element represented as static springs using continuum are applied to the structure and the assessment of variation in results are done. The analysis of multi-risers is usually done by assuming a fixed base as in most cases the foundation is taken to rest on rocky soils. The changes in design results due the assignment of soil springs are analysed in the present study.

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

The response of a structure is affected by interaction between three linked systems, the structure, the foundation and the soil underlying and surrounding the foundation. Soil-Structure interaction analysis evaluates the collective response of these systems to specified motion.

1.1 Background & Objectives:

The application of SSI for building structures is hindered by a literature that is often difficult to understand and codes and standards that contain limited guidance. Most of the methods of analysis use wave equations in several dimensions & complex arithmetic to formulate solutions & express results. This gives rise to present situation where soil structure interaction is seldom applied.

The purpose of the thesis is to develop guidance for implementing soil-structure interaction in the analysis and design of multi-risers such that the structural models include elements that account for the geotechnical and foundation conditions associated with buildings under consideration. Work also included an extensive study and review of available research on soil-structure interaction, evaluation of existing SSI guidelines.

Once the decision to implement SSI has been made, a basic level of understanding of the physical phenomenon and a practical analysis methodology for simulating the effects are needed. The thesis describes the principles of SSI in a clear and concise way and consistent nomenclature is used throughout. Explicit computational tools that can be used in engineering practice are provided and applications of SSI to force based analysis procedures and response spectrum analysis procedures are described.

As part of the work, soil structure interaction procedures were applied to detailed example applications to evaluate the influence of SSI components on the analysis results of dynamic load cases (as per IS 1893) and subsequently on the effect of the design of the structural members. Implementation of S.S.I within a design setting requires close collaboration between the structural and geotechnical engineers. Neither discipline alone is likely to have sufficient knowledge of structural, foundation and site considerations necessary to properly complete a meaningful analysis considering SSI effects.

1.2 Overview of Soil-Structure Interaction:

A SSI analysis evaluates the collective response of the structure, foundation and soil underlying and surrounding the foundation to a specified free field motion. The term free field refers to motions that are not affected by structural vibrations or scattering of waves at, and around the foundation. SSI effects are absent for the theoretical condition of rigid foundation supported on rigid soil. Accordingly SSI accounts for the difference between the actual response of structure and the response of the theoretical rigid base condition.

The terms kinematic and inertial interaction were introduced in 1975 by Robert Whitman (Kausel, 2010). These effects are related to the engineering analysis and design as follows:

1. Foundation stiffness and damping

Inertia developed in a vibrating structure gives rise to base shear, moment & torsion. These forces generate displacements and rotations at the soil-foundation interaction. These deformations are possible because of the flexibility in the soil-foundation system which significantly contributes to overall structural flexibility and increases the period of structure. These also give rise to energy dissipation via radiation damping and hysteretic soil damping which can significantly affect the overall damping. Since they are rooted in structural inertia it is called the inertial interaction effects.

2. Variations between foundation input motions and free field ground motions. Foundation input motion and free field motion differ because of

1) Kinematic interaction in which stiff foundation elements placed at or below the ground surface causes the foundation motion to differ from free field motions due to base slab averaging, wave scattering and embedment effects in the absence of structure and foundation inertia.

2) Relative displacements and rotations between the free field and foundation because of structure and foundation inertial effects.

Methods used to evaluate the above effects can be categorised as direct and superstructure method. In direct analysis the soil and structure are included within the same model and analysed as complete system. In a substructure approach the SSI is partitioned into distinct parts which are combined to formulate complete solutions.

Direct method:

As represented in figure soil is often represented as continuum (e.g., finite elements) along with foundation and structural elements, transmitting boundaries at the limits of soil mesh, and interface elements at the edges of foundation

Fig 1.1: Direct Method of evaluation

Evaluation of site response using wave propagation analysis through the soil is important to this approach. Such analyses are most often performed using an equivalent linear representation of soil properties in finite difference, finite element and boundary element numerical formulations.

Substructure approach:

Proper consideration of SSI effects in a substructure approach requires

- 1) Evaluation of free –field soil motions and corresponding soil material properties;
- 2) Evaluation of transfer functions to convert free-field motions to foundation input motions;
- 3) Incorporation of springs and dashpots(or more non-linear elements) to represent the stiffness and damping at the soil-foundation interface;
- 4) A response analysis of the combined structure-spring/dashpot system with the foundation input motion;

The steps in a substructure approach are as follows:

1) Specification of foundation input motion (FIM), which is the motion of the base slab that accounts for the stiffness and geometry of the structure. Because inertia is dealt with separately, the FIM applies for the theoretical condition of base slab and structure having no mass. This motion generally differs from the free field motion and represents the seismic demand applied to the foundation and structural system. The variation between the free field motion and the FIM is given by a transfer function that gives the ratio of foundation motion to free field motion. Since inertial effects are neglected transfer function represents kinematic interaction effect only. An essential step in defining the FIM is to evaluate the free field response of the site which is the spatial and temporal variation of ground motion in the absence of structure and foundation.

This task requires the earthquake input motion is known it either at a specific point or in the form of incident waves. Having established the free field motion, wave propagation analyses are performed to find the foundation input motion at the planned soil foundation interface. Equivalent linear properties of soil are assumed.

Fig 1.2: Substructure approach of analysis

- 2) The stiffness and damping characteristics of soil-foundation interaction are characterized using relatively simple impedance function models or a series of springs or dashpots. There are static springs used when the equivalent force method is used or the dampener, spring system used when the time history analysis is done.

- 3) The superstructure is modelled above the foundation and the system is excited through the foundation by displacing the ends of the springs using the rocking and translational motions.

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE REVIEW

Soil- structure interaction is the response of structures caused by the flexibility of the foundation soils as well as the variability in the response of soils caused due to the presence of substructure. Professor Kyoji Suyehiro was one of the first to discuss the variability of the building movements with the ground. He states that “very probably the primary cause is the yielding of the ground bed due to the oscillation of the foundation.”(1).The most common approach to modelling of superstructure is the fixed base which assumes infinite stiffness of foundation soils (2, 3, 4 and 5). A rigid base refers to soil supports with infinite stiffness (i.e. without soil supports).A rigid foundation refers to foundation elements with infinite stiffness.

A fixed base refers to a combination of a rigid foundation on a rigid base. The flexible base analysis considers the compliance (i.e. deformability) of both the foundation elements and the soil. Consider a single degree of freedom structure with stiffness k, mass m on a fixed base as depicted in fig. A static force F causes deformation δ (horizontal force),(6)

$$\delta = \frac{F}{k} \text{ -----} \quad 2.1$$

For structural dynamics, the undamped time period is given by:

$$T = \frac{2\pi}{\omega} = 2\pi\sqrt{\frac{m}{k}} \text{ -----} 2.2$$

Subst. eq.2.1 in eq. 2.2 & squaring

$$T^2 = ((2\pi)^2 * m) / \left(\frac{F}{\delta}\right)^2 \text{-----2.3}$$

Fig: 2.1 (a) An SDOF structural model with a flexible base (b) A replacement SDOF

Now consider the same structure with vertical, horizontal and rotational springs at base, representing the effects of soil flexibility against a rigid foundation. Now let k_h , k_z and k_r represent vertical springs in z, horizontal in x and rotational spring in x-z plane. If a force F is applied to the lumped mass in the x direction, the structure deflects, as it does in the fixed base system, but the base shear (F) deflects the horizontal spring by U_f and moment $F_h * h$ deflects the rotational spring by Θ . Accordingly the total deflection with respect to free field at the top of the structure,

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= F/k + U_f + \Theta * h \\
 &= F/k + F/k_h + (F * h) / k_r * h \text{ ----- eq.2.4}
 \end{aligned}$$

Subst. eq. 2.4 in eq. 2.3, the expression for flexible base is obtained as

$$\check{T}^2 = 2\pi^2 * m * \left(\frac{1}{k} + \frac{1}{k_h} + \frac{h^2}{k_r} \right) \text{ -----eq.2.5}$$

$$\frac{\check{T}}{T} = k * m * \left(\frac{1}{k} + \frac{1}{k_h} + \frac{h^2}{k_r} \right) \text{ -----eq.2.6}$$

It simplifies into classical period lengthening expression (Veletos and Meek, 1974)

$$\frac{\check{T}}{T} = \sqrt{1 + \frac{k}{k_h} + k * \frac{h^2}{k_r}} \text{ -----eq.2.7}$$

In addition to period lengthening, system behaviour is also affected by damping associated with soil foundation interaction, referred to as foundation damping, β_f . This is composed of two parts:

- (1) Contributions from soil hysteresis (hysteretic damping) (7) and
- (2) Radiation of energy in the form of stress waves, from the foundation. (Radiation energy)

Foundation damping is a direct contributor to flexible soil base system damping, β_o

$$\beta_o = \beta_f + \left(1/\frac{\dot{T}}{T}\right)^n * \beta_i$$

(8, 9)

Where β_i is the structural damping in the superstructure assuming a fixed base which is generally taken as 5% for typical structural systems. The refined estimates of β_i are possible based on structural system type & configuration, as described in (10). PEER/ATC-72-1, Modelling and Acceptance criteria for seismic design and analysis of tall buildings (ATC, 2010). Analytical models for foundation damping have been presented by Veletos & Nair (1975), Bielak (1975 & 1976), Rosset (1980), Wolf (1985), Aviles & Perez-Rocha (1996), Marvas et.al (2007) and Givens (2013), among others. Solution of Veletos and Nair accounts for the frequency dependence of foundation damping terms. It assumes the damping to be viscous and applies for a circular foundation on a half space. The equation provided for β_f is complex valued which complicates the interpretation. Bielak's work utilizes the same conditions except that the foundation is a cylinder penetrating a half space to embedment depth D, and the resulting expressions are real valued. The procedure given by Wolf (1985) neglects frequency dependence of foundation stiffness terms, and assumed foundation damping to be linearly viscous (i.e. constant dashpot constants for translation and rotation) and applies for a circular foundation on half space. Considering frequency dependence, the form of Wolf's damping expression can be re-written as

$$\beta_f = \left(\frac{\left(\frac{\dot{T}}{T}\right)^{n_s} - 1}{\frac{\dot{T}}{T}}\right) * \beta_s + \left(\frac{1}{\left(\frac{\dot{T}}{T_x}\right)^{n_x}}\right) * \beta_x + \left(\frac{1}{\frac{\dot{T}}{T_{yy}}^{n_{yy}}}\right) * \beta_{yy}$$

β_s = soil hysteresis damping

β_x and β_{yy} are damping ratios related to radiation damping from translational & rotational

$$T_x = 2\pi\sqrt{(m/k_x)} \text{ and } T_{yy} = 2\pi\sqrt{((mh^2)/k_{yy})}$$

ns, nx, nyy terms are expected to take a value of 2. (Givens 2013)

2.1 Soil Structure interaction models

Basically there are two types of derivation approaches used for models of SSI problems ;(11,12)

Structural and continuum approach. The structural approach has a rigid base from which subgrade and superstructure are built. The structural approach has a rigid base from which subgrade and superstructure are built. The subgrade is represented by dampeners, springs etc. and superstructure by flexural elements. The other alternative continuum approach is based on three partially-differential equations-(compatibility, constitutive and equilibrium) which are governing the behaviour for the subgrade as continuum (Teodoru, 2009).When combining the two derivational approaches, the method is called hybrid derivational approach.

1) Elastic continuum

In elastic continuum mechanics, continuum is defined by a continuously distributed matter through space. The analytical solution for several loading cases has been developed for semi-infinite elastic continuum. The solution for point and distributed load was given Boussinesque, Timoshenko and Goodier (1970). However subgrade with shallow depth is poorly described with the cone model analytical methods.

Reissner's equation for elastic medium with height H, elasticity E_s and shear modulus G with distributed load q and vertical surface displacement w at any point is given by

$$q(x, y) = ((G*H^2)/(12*E_s))*\Delta^2$$

$$q(x, y) = E_s*w(x, y)/H - (G*H/3)*\Delta^2 * w(x,y)$$

It has the drawbacks like:

- 1) The medium is assumed to be weightless.

2) Horizontal, normal and shear stresses are zero. Hence it is applicable to be applied at the top of surface.

A continuum can be approximately be analysed with numerical methods. The numerical methods FEM and boundary element method (BEM) are suitable for SSI analysis. (13, 14)

2.2 Winker Model (15)

Today the most well-known and used foundation model for SSI analysis, by structural engineers, is the Winkler model. It is also the oldest and simplest method to model the subgrade which consists of infinite number of springs on a rigid base. For a structural model there will be a finite number of springs, see Figure 2.1. (Horvath and Colasanti, 2011).

The Winkler model is easy to implement in a structural system. In a 2D structure, beam elements on top of the subgrade are attached to a spring at each node. The springs are only affecting the structure in vertical direction. Every spring is attached to two nodes, but since the lower nodes are fixed, those nodes can be removed from the equations, i.e. no nodes “outside” the superstructure’s geometry are added to the system of equations.

The stiffness of a discrete spring k_1 can be estimated with different approaches, but is always defined as a relation between the settlement, and reaction force R_1 in a point. For one specific point the relation can be written as:

$$k_1 = R_1/\delta$$

Where δ is the displacement

In a simple model, the spring stiffness can be assumed to be uniformly distributed. A normal approximation, presented by SGI (1993), for calculation of settlements is to assume a 2:1 stress distribution in the soil. The stiffness for discrete springs is calculated by dividing the vertical load affecting one spring $q*s$ by settlement, where s is the spacing between the springs. With uniform spring stiffness, constant modulus E , through the depth in the soil and assuming 2:1 stress distribution,

Winkler Model

Figure 4.5.2 Equivalent foundation resting on Winkler spring bed.

Figure 2.2 Visualisation of a structural Winkler model.

Winkler model is the simplest structural model, but also the least accurate. The primary deficiency of the model is that the shear capacity of the soil is neglected. As a result of omitting the shear stresses, displacement has no spread in transverse direction. Therefore displacement discontinuity appears between loaded and unloaded surfaces. In reality soil has a shear capacity and no displacement discontinuity occurs.

An immediate consequence of the lack of shear transfer is concerning the foundation stiffness at the superstructure's edges. What should be noted is the high pressure at the edges. To emulate this behaviour with Winkler model, the springs can be given a higher stiffness at the edges. Adopting uniform spring stiffness distribution gives greater settlements and sectional forces towards the edges. These results would be on the safe side in this case, but the ground pressure would be unconservative.

As the foundation's stiffness distribution is pronounced non-uniform for an elastic continuum, it can result in different overall SSI-behaviour compared to model with uniform stiffness. The previous SSI comparison, Bolteus (1984) showed with numerical analysis a difference in settlement profile with comparing a Winkler model with an elastic semi-infinite continuum model. The Winkler model gave convex settlement profile and the continuum model a concave profile. Commonly observed in reality is a concave profile, i.e. opposite to the Winkler model. As a result of deviating settlement profile for the two models, different load transfers in superstructure occur. Differences in result for the two methods are presented in detail in Bolteus (1984).

2.3 Multi-Parameter Models (16)

To capture the shear transfer in the soil with a structural model, it becomes logical to introduce an interacting element to couple the independent springs in the Winkler model, see Figure 2.2.

Fig 2.3: Multi-parametric model

Several structural models have been developed to include load transfer in transverse direction. The interaction elements can be springs, flexural elements, shear layer, pre-tensioned membranes etc. When interaction elements are introduced between the springs, several parameters characterize the subgrade's response, and are there called multi-parameter models. Some developed multi-parameter models are presented in Table 2.1.

Table 2.1 Compiling of multi-parameter models. Adapted from (Hovarth, 2002).

Subgrade model	Physical elements used to visualise model
Winkler's Hypothesis	Springs
Filonenko-Borodich	Deformed, pre-tensioned membrane + springs
Pastermak's Hypothesis	Shear layer + springs
Loof's Hypothesis	
Kerr model	Springs + shear layer + springs
Haber-Shaim	Plate + springs
Hetenyi	Springs + plate + springs
Rhines	Springs + plate + shear layer + springs
Timoshenko beam	Beam

The Timoshenko beam, which captures both bending and shear deformation, can be used as an interaction element, which is characterised by only shear deformation, only bending deformation or a combination of the two.

Claes Alen (1998) discusses an interaction element that is represented as a beam characterized by its shear stiffness and with infinite bending stiffness, i.e. a shear layer. A problem with such a beam is that its properties cannot be set for a beam in several commercial software (FEM-Design included), as the value of the G-modules is in relation to the E-modulus with Poisson's ratio. A similar principle that Alen describes can instead of a beam be treated with connecting "shear springs" in between every "main spring" couple. The resulting stiffness matrix to handle the vertical reaction forces becomes the same for Alen's model and for the system with shear springs visualised. This subgrade model transfers shear to parts outside the superstructure's boundaries, i.e. additional main springs than directly under the superstructure carry load. This must be considered when determining the stiffness. As the main springs and the shear-springs are affecting each other, their stiffness cannot be determined independently.

If adopting the 2:1 method to determine the stiffness of the main springs, the shear spring stiffness would have to be approximately zero or else the settlements would be underestimated compared to the elastic continuum solution. A lower limit would be to assume that there is no spread of the stress when determining the main spring stiffness, which is true for a case with infinite and constant load propagation. The stress distribution is instead only considered in the model, where the shear springs distribute load between the main springs, when assuming uniform spring stiffness and constant E- modulus in the soil.

Fig2.4 Kerr model

2.4 Hybrid Model

As described in previous sections, there are pros and cons for both structural models and continuum model. The structural models are easy to model, but the simple ones have a lack of accuracy. The more complex models are improved, but the difficulty to estimate realistic parameters increases. The continuum model is more accurate for soil modelling and geotechnical engineers have relatively accurate methods to evaluate its parameters, but the model can be difficult to implement in today's existing structural design software (Horvath and Colasanti, 2011).

By studying Reissner's differential equation that describes vertical force-displacement behaviour for a simplified continuum, Kerr has developed a structural model with an equation on a similar form. Kerr's model is visualized with two spring layers and an incompressible shear layer in between.

Fig 2.4

(a) Modified Kerr mechanical subgrade model

Fig 2.5 Hybrid model

According to Horvath (2002), Kerr's shear layer is not possible to implement in most commercial software. Kerr's shear layer is structurally equivalent to a deformed, pre-tensioned membrane. Horvath describes a modified Kerr's model which is named Modified Kerr-Reissner (MK-R). In the MK-R model the setup is the same as in Kerr's model, but the shear layer is replaced with a pre-tensioned membrane, see Figure 2.4.

It should be noted that the analysis must include secondary effects; otherwise the pre-tensioned membrane won't be regarded properly.

2.5 Finite Element Analysis

F.E.A is a numerical method. It is also referred to as Finite Element Method. The solution of the problems using finite element method requires the solution to partial differential equations using boundary value problems. The method yields approximate values of the unknown at discrete no of points over domain. The steps involved are:

- a) A large problem is divided into smaller simpler parts called finite elements.
- b) The simple equations that model these finite elements are then assembled into a larger system of equations that models the entire problem.

The soil is assumed to be made of 3D or 2D elements.

2.6 Semi – Analytical and Analytical methods (17, 18, 19)

Continuum methods are based on the theory of wave propagation in elastic or viscoelastic solid (continuum). The first study is done by Lamb on the vibrations of elastic semi- infinite solid (half-space) caused by concentrated load. Reissner attempted the first application, his publication on the response of vertically loaded cylindrical disk on elastic half-space marks the beginning of application of the approach on soil mechanics. His assumption of contact stresses was uniform. In this the theory is based on the concept that every time a foundation moves against soil, stress waves originate at the surface and propagate outwards in the form of waves. To closer approximate the rigid body motion, contact stress distribution is taken as linear. Sung and Quilan presented results for vertically oscillating circular and rectangular foundations while Arnold and et al and Byerrot studied for horizontal and vertical loadings. Important theoretical developments came when Hsieh and Lysmer used a S.D.O.F mass-spring –dashpot oscillator with frequency dependent stiffness and damping coefficients. Richart and Whitman extended Lysmer’s analogue by demonstrating that all modes of vibration can be studied by means of lumped – parameter – mass-spring-dashpot system.

2.7 Preference of Continuum method over Finite Element Method (20), (21) and (22)

The finite element models available are 3D solid elements, axis symmetric solid elements & 2D plane strain elements. F.E.A can be used to solve a large class of problems like non – regular foundation shapes, inclined layering in soil deposits. Embedment effects, coupling between dissimilar embedment structures.

For damping consideration, only element damping takes place but damping is internal and radiation is into unbound medium.

One of the reasons for use of F.E.A is the capacity of finite elements to incorporate strain dependent soil properties.

- 1) The first step in this procedure is a linear dynamic analysis of the soil structure system using estimated values.
- 2) The initial values are obtained using “ $1\frac{D}{27}$ wave propagation theory”.
- 3) Process is repeated till the desired accuracy.

The continuum methods involve the elimination of frequency dependency of the impedance functions & the use of constant impedance functions.

A simplification of system damping is done to use normal mode method to solve the equations of motion. This step enables the calculation of equivalent modal damping values. If it is not possible to find the appropriate equivalent damping values, equations of motions are solved by direct integration techniques, transform method or Foss method.

F.E.A has limitations like box & radiation damping effects, filtering of the higher frequencies. This is even important when the strain dependency of the soil properties is not even rigorously incorporated into the finite element approach.

Chapter 3

Models considered and analysis methodology

3.1 Introduction

This chapter defines the different models studied. It defines the analysis methodology, material properties, general kinematic properties, building geometry considered for the analysis purposes. The models are G+20, G+30, G+50 for the same plan. 3-D frame models are considered to study the variation in design due to the soil-structure interaction phenomenon.

3.1.1 General properties of models

1. Material properties

a) Density of concrete = 25 Kn/m^3

b) Density of steel = 7850 Kg/m^3

c) $E_c = 5000 \sqrt{f_{ck}}$

2. Frame section

a) Material: M25

b) Cover:

1) Top = 75 mm

2) Bottom = 75 mm

3. Loads

1) Earthquake Loads: EQXP, EQYP, EQXN, EQYN

Type: Quake

EQXP: X direction + eccentricity

EQXN: X direction - eccentricity

EQYP: Y direction + eccentricity

EQYN: Y direction – eccentricity

Eccentricity=0.005

Time period = $0.009h/\sqrt{d}$

IS 1893 (Part 1): 2002, clause 7.6

Story range: Ground floor to top floor

Seismic coefficients:

Zone: 3

IS 1893 (Part 1)

Soil type: 2 (medium)

Importance factor =1.5

R=3

2) Wind Analysis

Wind loads: W_x, W_y

Wind speed= 44m/s

Structure class =A

IS 875(part 3)

3) Self-weight

The software Etaabs assigns the self-weight forces of the structural members as per the material property assigned.

IS 875(part 1)

4) Wall loads

External wall loads

Thickness of external wall=200mm

Material= Siporex

Density=8KN/m³

External plaster=24mm

Internal plaster=12mm

Total plaster=26mm

Density of mortar= 24 KN/m³

Wall load/m =9.37 KN/m³

Internal wall loads

Thickness of internal wall=150mm

Material = Siporex

Density = 8 KN/m^3

Internal plaster = 12mm

Total plaster = 24mm

Density of mortar = 24 KN/m^3

Wall load/m = 6.75 KN/m^3

5) Staircase load

L.L = 3 KN/m^2

6) Live Loads considered:

Classrooms = 3 Passages,

lobbies = 4 KN/m^2

Storeroom = 5 KN/m^2

Staff/Office = 2.5 KN/m^2

L.L Reduction = 3

Mass source=0.5

7) Load combinations:

1) $1.5(D.L + L.L)$

2) $1.2(D.L + L.L + EQXP)$

3) $1.2(D.L + L.L + EQXN)$

4) $1.2(D.L + L.L + EQYP)$

5) $1.2(D.L + L.L + EQYN)$

6) $1.2(D.L + L.L - EQXP)$

7) $1.2(D.L + L.L - EQXN)$

8) $1.2(D.L + L.L - EQYP)$

9) $1.2(D.L + L.L - EQYN)$

10) $1.2(D.L + L.L + WX)$

11) $1.2(D.L + L.L + WY)$

12) $1.2(D.L + L.L - WX)$

13) $1.2(D.L + L.L - WY)$

14) $1.5(D.L + EQXP)$

15) $1.5(D.L + EQXN)$

16) $1.5(D.L + EQYP)$

17) $1.5(D.L + EQYN)$

18) $1.5(D.L - EQXP)$

19) $1.5(D.L - EQXN)$

20) $1.5(D.L - EQYP)$

21) $1.5(D.L - EQYN)$

22) $0.9D.L + 1.5 L.L$

Where

1) D.L = Dead load

2) L.L = Live load

3) EQXP = Earthquake Load in X direction + positive eccentricity in Y-direction

4) EQXN = Earthquake Load in X direction + negative eccentricity in Y-direction

5) EQYP = Earthquake Load in Y direction + positive eccentricity in X-direction

6) EQYN = Earthquake Load in Y direction + negative eccentricity in X-direction

X-direction

3.1.2 Building Geometry

The study is based on 3D models of a structural plan with varying storey heights. The structures are modelled by using computer software Etaabs. The foundation dimensions were arrived at using software SAFE.

The gravity loads are calculated from the material and section properties of elements. The loads are factored. The various load combinations used in the analysis are defined in the previous section.

Beams and Columns are modelled by using 2D frame elements. The properties of sections are selected from the list of properties. The slabs are designed as diaphragms. Etaabs uses Stiffness matrix method for line objects' analysis and finite element analysis for plates.

Some basic Concepts of stiffness matrix method:

1) Node:

The more general name for a connection between adjacent members is termed a node. For trusses and frames the terms joint and node are interchangeable. For more complex structures (e.g. plates), they are not.

2) Element:

For trusses and frames element means the same as member. For more complex structures this is not the case.

3) Degree of Freedom:

The number of possible directions that displacements or forces at a node can exist in is termed a degree of freedom (dof). Some examples are:

- plane truss: has 3 degrees of freedom at each node: the translations/forces similar to a plane truss and in addition, the rotation or moment at the joint

Fig 3.1: Plane truss with the corresponding degrees of freedom

- Beams: have 2 degrees of freedom per node: vertical displacement/forces and rotation/moment.

Fig 3.2: Beam with the corresponding degrees of freedom

- Plane Frame: has 3 degrees of freedom at each node: the translations/forces similar to a plane truss and in addition, the rotation or moment at the joint

Fig 3.3: Plane frame with corresponding degrees of freedom

Space Frame: has 6 degrees of freedom at each node: translation/forces along each axis, and rotation/moments about each axis.

Fig 3.4: Space frame with corresponding degrees of freedom

- Space Truss: a truss in three dimensions has 3 degrees of freedom: translation or forces along each axis in space.

Fig 3.5 Space truss with corresponding degrees of freedom

3.1.3 Shear walls and meshing

Shear wall is assigned as a shell. The meshing of wall is done such that each mesh is of size not greater than 1.5 m and less than 1m. A study of mesh element sizes & accuracy of results shows that the one with width of 1-1.5m & height of story depth is found to give the most consistent results.

3.2 Analysis methodology

This section explains the analysis methodologies.

For the seismic analysis of structures, the following methods are available:

3.2.1 Seismic coefficient method:

This is the simplest of the methods of analysis of structures. In this seismic effect on structures is analysed by considering a system of equivalent lateral loads acting on the structure. An elastic analysis is performed on the structure and it is ensured that the stresses are within the permissible limits. The total weight of the structure is taken and is multiplied by the seismic coefficient which is dependent on several parameters. This seismic force calculated is distributed over the height of the structure such that the maximum lateral force equal to the base shear gets applied at the top most storey level. The horizontal seismic coefficient given as A_h is given by,

$$A_h = (Z/2) * (I/R) * S_a/g$$

Where, Z = Zone factor

I = Importance factor

R = Response reduction factor.

S_a/g = Response acceleration coefficient.

The total horizontal load, also known as the base shear is then taken as,

$$V_b = A_h \times W$$

Where, W is the Seismic weight of the structure (Dead load).

The base shear is calculated above is then distributed along the height of the building using

The formula $Q_i = V_b \times W_i h_i^2 / \sum W_i h_i^2$

Where,

Q_i is the lateral force at the top of floor i

W_i is the total of dead and appropriate amount of live load at the top of floor i.

h_i is the height measured from the base of the building to the top of floor i.

The results given by the seismic coefficient are very conservative. The method is very widely referred because of the simplicity of the procedure. It can be used for the analysis of moderate earthquakes where the analysis is elastic.

Fig 3.6: Distribution of earthquake forces along the height of the structure

3.2.2 Response Spectrum method

The response spectrum gives the varied accelerative response with respect to the frequencies. It can be visualized as the plotting of the peak acceleration of a no of oscillators with varying frequencies. (23)

Knowing the natural frequency of a system the response is picked from the plot.

Derivation of equation for response spectrum:

(24)

Equation of motion for a single degree of freedom can be written as

$$m\ddot{u} + c\dot{u} + ku = -m\ddot{u}_g(t) \quad \text{Eq.1}$$

Where

u is displacement relative to the ground.

Eqn. (1) can be written as modal equation

$$\ddot{u} + 2\xi\omega\dot{u} + \omega^2 u = -\ddot{u}_g(t)$$

where

$$\omega = \sqrt{k/m}$$

$$\xi = 2c/\omega\sqrt{m} < 1$$

Ground acceleration $\ddot{u}_g$ is assumed to be linear over a time step i :

Let's define slope, s , of the acceleration within a time step as

$$s = \ddot{u}_g(t_i) - \ddot{u}_g(t_{i-1})/t_i - t_{i-1} \text{ and time step independent time variable, } t, \text{ as}$$

$$t = t - t_{i-1}$$

The above equations can be combined together to give the following equation:

$$u''(t) + 2\xi\omega u'(t) + \omega^2 u(t) = -u''_{g(t)} - st \quad \text{Eq 2}$$

with initial conditions

$$u(t) \text{ for } t=0 \quad \text{(a)}$$

$$u'(t) \text{ for } t=0 \quad \text{(b)}$$

The solution of Equation (2) with initial conditions (a) and (b) will be obtained as a sum of homogeneous and particular solution $u = u_h + u_p$

The final solution is

$$u(t) = e^{-\xi\omega t} (C_1 \cos(\omega_d t) + C_2 \sin(\omega_d t)) + Et + F$$

Where

$$C_1 = u(t_{i-1}) - F$$

$$C_2 = (u'(t_{i-1}) + \xi\omega C_1 - E) / \omega_d$$

$$E = -s / \omega^2$$

$$F = (1 / \omega^2) * ((2\xi / \omega) s - u''_{g(t_{i-1})})$$

$$s = (u''_{g(t_i)} - u''_{g(t_{i-1})}) / (t_i - t_{i-1})$$

$$\omega_d = \omega \sqrt{1 - \xi^2}$$

Numerous attempts have been made to extend the applicability of the method for inelastic response under severe earthquakes. The response spectrum is a plot of the maximum response (usually the acceleration S_a) of single degree of freedom (SDOF) system as a function of its natural period T . For design purposes, the smoothed average of a number of elastic response spectrums corresponding to various possible earthquakes at a particular site, known as the smoothed elastic design response spectrum (SEDRS), is used. The SEDRS is further

simplified so that it can be represented by a set of equations corresponding to different period ranges. SEDRS are usually specified for different soil conditions. Most structures, such as multi-storeyed buildings are multi degree of freedom (MDOF) systems whose response can be approximated by considering only the first few natural modes. The fact is used to great advantage in modal spectral analysis, where the first few natural vibration mode shapes are calculated as a first step, Each mode can then be considered to represent the vibration shape of an SDOF with a corresponding natural period and so its maximum response can be directly determined from the response spectrum. The total response of the structure can then be calculated as combination of these individual responses. A variety of ways are available to combine the individual responses considering the fact that these maximum responses occur at different instant of time. When the natural period are sufficiently apart, the most common way of combining the maximum responses is by taking the square root of the sum of the squares (SRSS) method.

Types of combination methods as per the Indian codal provisions,

The peak response quantities (eg. Member forces, displacements, storey forces, storey shears and base reactions) should be combined as per the complete quadratic combination (CQC) method (clause 7.8.4.4)

$$\tilde{\lambda} = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^r \sum_{j=1}^r \tilde{\lambda}_i \hat{\rho}_{ij} \tilde{\lambda}_j}$$

Where r is the number of modes being considered, $\hat{\rho}_{ij}$ is the cross modal coefficient given by the succeeding equation, $\tilde{\lambda}_i$ is the response quantity in mode i and $\tilde{\lambda}_j$ is the response quantity in mode j (including sign).

$$\hat{\rho}_{ij} = \frac{8\delta^2(1 + \beta)\beta^{1.5}}{(1 - \beta^2)^2 + 4\delta^2\beta(1 + \beta)^2}$$

Alternatively, the peak response quantities may be combined by the SRSS method (clause 7.8.4.4(a)) as in case 1 and ABS method (clause 7.8.4.4(b)) as in case 2 as follows:

Case 1 if the building does not have closely spaced mode, the peak response quantity λ due to all modes considered should be obtained as

$$\lambda = \sqrt{\sum_{k=1}^r \lambda_k^2}$$

Where λ_k is the absolute value of the quantity in mode k and r is the number of modes being considered.

Case 2 If the building has a few closely spaced modes, the peak response quantities λ^* due to these modes should be obtained as

$$\lambda^* = \sum_c^r \lambda_c$$

The ABS method gives the absolute maximum and hence the results are very conservative.

Hence the SRSS can be very safely be used.

3.2.3 Pushover analysis:

The analysis involves applying horizontal loads in a prescribed pattern to the structure incrementally until the peak response of the structure is obtained or pushing the structure till target displacement is reached and plotting the total applied shear force and associated lateral displacement at each incremental until the collapse condition. The equivalent static lateral

loads or the lateral displacement approximately represents earthquake induced forces or displacement. A plot of the total base shear versus roof displacement in a structure is obtained by this analysis that would indicate any premature failure or weakness. The analysis is carried out up to failure thus it enables determination of collapse load and ductility capacity curve, for a structure or structural element. The plastic rotation is also monitored in this method.

3.2.4 Time History Analysis.

Time History analysis is a step by step analysis of the dynamical response of a structure to a specified loading that may vary with time. The analysis may be linear or nonlinear. Time history analysis is used to determine the dynamic response of a structure to arbitrary loading. Time history analysis is explained in detail in further topic.

Time-history analysis is a step-by-step analysis of the dynamical response (in time domain) of a structure subjected to a specified ground motion. This section explains the nonlinear parameters, input ground motion, time integration and damping used in the present study. The dynamic input has been given as a ground acceleration time-history which is applied uniformly at all the points of the base of the structure; only one horizontal component of the ground motion has been considered. The present softwares like SAP2000, Etaabs can be used for carrying out nonlinear time-history analysis. Time- history analysis is used to determine the dynamic response of a structure to arbitrary loading. The dynamic equilibrium equations to be solved are given by:

$$K u(t) + C \dot{u}(t) + M \ddot{u}(t) = r(t)$$

Where K is the stiffness matrix;

C is the damping matrix;

M is the diagonal mass Matrix

$u(t)$ represent the displacements and the corresponding velocities and accelerations of the structure found by the successive differentiations and r is the applied load.

If the load includes ground acceleration, the displacements, velocities, and accelerations are relative to this ground motion. Any number of time- history Load Cases can be defined. Each time-history case can differ in the load applied and in the type of analysis to be performed.

Below are the methods which can be used for solving the equation of motions: (Direct integration)

(a) Newmark-beta method

In time history analysis procedures there are a number of ways to numerically integrate the fundamental equation of motion. The Newmark-beta method is a method of numerical integration used to solve differential equations. The Newmark method of numerical integration is considered a generalization of the linear acceleration method. It is widely used in numerical evaluation of the dynamic response of structures and solids such as in finite element analysis to model dynamic systems.

(b) The HHT- α method

HHT- α method is a generalization of the Newmark β method and reduces to the Newmark- β method for $\alpha = 0$. The HHT- α method adopts the finite difference equations of the Newmark- β method, the equations of motion are modified, however, using a parameter α , which represents a numerical lag in the damping, stiffness, nonlinear, and external forces. For poorly converging nonlinear time-history cases, the Hilber Hughes-Taylor (HHT) method with $0 < \alpha \leq -1/3$. During HHT application, when $\alpha = 0$, formulation is identical to the average acceleration method, so HHT will actually suffice for all problems.

c) Wilson- Θ method

The Wilson- Θ Method is a linear multistep method for second order equations. The Wilson Theta method assumes that the acceleration of the system varies linearly between two instants of time. The acceleration is assumed to be linear between successive time intervals. Because of this reason the method is known as the Wilson Theta method.

3.2.5 Wind Effects on structures (25)

The wind effect on structures can be classified into two:

(a) Static effect

Static wind effects include elastic bending and twisting.

(b) Dynamic effect

For tall, long span and slender structures, a dynamic analysis is essential. Wind gusts cause fluctuating forces which induce large scale dynamic motion.

Fig 3.7: Wind pressure distribution over the height of the structure

Determination of static wind loads as per IS 875:

$$\text{Design wind speed} = V_b * k_1 * k_2 * k_3$$

V_b = Design wind speed

k_1 = probability factor

k_2 = terrain height and structure size factor

k_3 = topography factor

The various parameters in wind load analysis are explained as follows

1) Averaging period

Anemometers help to measure wind speed. The response time for mechanical anemometer is 1-3 seconds. Several countries use 3 sec gust as the averaging period of basic wind speed. Dunst curve which has been in use since 1960 helps to find the wind speed for different averaging periods.

2) Return period

Wind speeds are amenable to statistical analysis. It is common for statistical Analysis of historical information adjusted on theoretical basis to be used in determining winds over long periods.

For temporary structures return period of two years is considered sufficient.

3) Ground roughness

The wind speeds are very much influenced by the ground roughness.

Experimental results showing variation in wind values at similar heights but different topographical conditions are available. There is reduced wind speed And also due to turbulence there is variation in wind directions causing change in average wind speed.

4) Height of the structure

The gust wind analysis is often required to be carried out for the tall structures As there is the an added phenomenon of wind layer separation and formation of vortices which can cause considerable lateral drift.

5) Topography

It is well recognised in most wind loading standards. Wind load modelling And large scale tests in real environment is done to find the effect of topography. In general structures at the crests of ridges and near the edges of

escarpments experience higher wind speeds than the ambient. There is Also an interaction due to sheltering in enclosed basins and leeward side of basins.

The wind pressure can be approximated by:

$$\text{Pressure} = \frac{1}{2} \times (\text{density of air}) \times (\text{wind speed})^2 \times (\text{shape factor})$$

The density of air is about 1.25 kg/m^3

The shape factor (drag coefficient) depends on the shape of the body. It has order of magnitude 1 and is dimension less.

The wind speed must be expressed in m/s.

3.2.6 Introduction to ETABS

The software used for the present study Etabas. It is product of computers and Structures, Berkeley, USA. It is used for analysing general structures including bridges, stadiums, towers, industrial plants, offshore structures, buildings, dams, silos, etc. It is a fully integrated program that allows model creation, modification, execution of analysis, design, optimization, and results review from within a single interface. ETABS is a finite element based structural program for analysis and design of civil structures. It offers an intuitive, yet powerful user interface with many tools to aid in quick and accurate construction of models, along with sophisticated technique needed to do most complex projects. Results for analysis and design are reported for the overall structure providing information that is both easier to interpret and consistent with physical nature.

A) Procedure for P delta Analysis

1) Go to Analyse → Set Analysis Options

Fig 3.8: Selection of analysis option from the analyse dialog box

2) In the Analysis Options dialog box check the Include P-Delta Dialog box

Fig 3.9: Selection of P-Delta dialog box

2) P-Delta Parameters dialog box lists the methods of analysis for the effect. The method preferred for the cases with gravitational loads under diaphragm action is the Iterative method.

Fig 3.10: Selection of Iterative Based Load combination method from P- delta dialog box

3) The load combination chosen is $1.5D.L + 0.9L.L$ and the right n. of iterations has to be chosen so the iteration can be completed.

(B) Procedure for response spectrum method:

- 1) In Define → Define Static Load cases → Define the required static load cases for earthquake analysis. The IS Code provisions state that

Fig 3.11: Selection and defining of static load cases

2) The load combination EQXP is defined in the following manner. XP denotes a load in X direction with an eccentricity of 5% the lateral dimension.

Fig 3.12: Definition of Earthquake load case

- 3) The seismic coefficients defined are as follows: Codal provision for Mumbai zone
 $Z=0.24$

Soil type 1 reason response reduction factor of 5

- 4) The response spectrum function is defined by going to define → Define Response Spectrum Function → Choose function type to add → IS 1893 2002 Spectrum.

Fig 3.13: Definition of Response spectrum function

5) The IS 1893 response curve is given as shown as given:

Fig 3.14: Response spectrum IS 1892: 2002

- 6) Further define the response spectrum defined load cases shown as below.
Under Define → Response Spectrum Cases

Fig 3.15: Selection of Response spectrum case from the Define dialog box

7) The following load cases are defined with the earthquake lateral force acting in X, Y direction with 5% eccentricity.

Fig 3.16: Define Earthquake load cases

8) The scale factor defined in the dialogue box corresponds to the seismic coefficient

Fig 3.17: Definition of the parameters used in earthquake load cases

2) Under the load cases the following parameters are defined

Fig 3.19: Definition of Wind load parameters

3.2.7 SAFE ANALYSIS

Foundation Analysis

The analysis report presents the total reactions at the foundation level in the form of vertical reactions FX , FY , FZ, MX , MY, MZ

1) The reaction forces for G+20 are as shown:

Fig 3.20: Support Reactions for G+20

Fig 3.21: Support Reactions for G+30

2) The reaction forces at supports for G+50:

Fig 3.22: Support Reactions for G+50

- The reactions forces when studied show the need for the raft foundation on rocky strata.
- The foundation analysis and dimensioning is undertaken by using the software safe.

Raft foundation analysis:

Define:

Define material C30 with the properties as shown below:

Define Reinforcement as shown below:

Fig 3.23: Definition of Material property data for foundation

Define subgrade property as shown below:

Fig 3.25: Definition of subgrade properties

The soil subgrade modulus = $S.B.C / \text{permissible settlement}$

IS 1904 (1986) Code of practise for design & construction of foundation in soils can referred for the permissible deflection for raft foundation in soils.

Max settlement for the raft foundation on sand/hard soil is 75mm.

The Safe Bearing Capacity of the soil is 100 t/m^2 (1000 KN/m^2) (Reference: IS-1892, Code of Practice for site Investigations for Foundations)

The soil subgrade modulus gets calculated as Safe bearing capacity/missible deflection

Checks on foundation:

- 1) The dimensioning of the raft has to be done such that there are no tensile stresses at the bottom.
- 2) The lateral forces of earthquake forces and wind are considered for design with the load cases changed to non-linear cases considering uplift. The non-linear cases considering uplift considering the springs to be compression only hence neglecting the tensile stresses.

1) Conversion to non-linear cases

Fig 3.26: Conversion of load cases to non-linear load cases

- 3) D.L+ L.L load combination is used to check against the development of tensile stresses at the bottom.

Fig 3.27: Check of the foundation against the development of uplifting forces

3.3.1 SSI Analysis

The soil springs are assigned at the foundation to account for the stiffness of soil in translations and rotations along x, y, z.

The springs in 6 directions are assigned because of the reaction forces F_X , F_Y , F_Z , M_X , M_Y , M_Z that are developed.

In the last 20 years a number of techniques have been developed for computing and using foundation impedances. Extensive reviews of these developments were presented by Lysmer (1978), Roessett (1980), Luco (1982), Gazetas (1983), Novak (1987), and Pais and Kausel (1988). The presently available methods include: (1) Analytical solutions based on integral transform techniques;

(2) Semi analytical and boundary-element formulations requiring discretization of only the top surface; (3) dynamic finite-element methods using special "wave transmitting" lateral boundaries; and (4) hybrid methods combining analytical and finite-element approaches.

The stiffness values of the soil springs calculated are as follows:

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Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	Ibx(m ⁴)	Iby(m ⁴)			Ibz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	4.5	7.412	33.354	81	0.4118	0.8	0.514040313	152.69946	56.284875	208.98433	3697575818	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	4.5	7.412	33.354	81	0.4118	0.8	0.514040313	152.69946	56.284875	208.98433	17961454461	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	4.5	7.412	33.354	81	0.4118	0.8	0.514040313	152.69946	56.284875	208.98433	18318839581	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	4.5	7.412	33.354	81	0.4118	0.8	0.514040313	152.69946	56.284875	208.98433	52145923392	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	4.5	7.412	33.354	81	0.4118	0.8	0.514040313	152.69946	56.284875	208.98433	24132060310	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	4.5	7.412	33.354	81	0.4118	0.8	0.514040313	152.69946	56.284875	208.98433	3.01434E+11	krz

Point 4

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	Ibx(m ⁴)	Iby(m ⁴)			Ibz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	10.1	7.46	75.346	408.04	0.1847	0.8	0.281687838				6347419863	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	10.1	7.46	75.346	408.04	0.1847	0.8	0.281687838				33185137344	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	10.1	7.46	75.346	408.04	0.1847	0.8	0.281687838				32861134350	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	10.1	7.46	75.346	408.04	0.1847	0.8	0.281687838	349.42712			1.01853E+11	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	10.1	7.46	75.346	408.04	0.1847	0.8	0.281687838		640.50379		1.68631E+11	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	10.1	7.46	75.346	408.04	0.1847	0.8	0.281687838			989.93091	1.30486E+12	krz

Point 33

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4I ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	Ibx(m ⁴)	Iby(m ⁴)			Ibz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	5.6	7.49	41.944	125.44	0.3344	0.8	0.439719119				4255313663	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	5.6	7.49	41.944	125.44	0.3344	0.8	0.439719119				21087817039	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	5.6	7.49	41.944	125.44	0.3344	0.8	0.439719119				21319773727	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	5.6	7.49	41.944	125.44	0.3344	0.8	0.439719119	196.08855			63083392347	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	5.6	7.49	41.944	125.44	0.3344	0.8	0.439719119		109.61365		41045304134	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	5.6	7.49	41.944	125.44	0.3344	0.8	0.439719119			305.7022	4.27724E+11	krz

Point 6

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4I ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	Ibx(m ⁴)	Iby(m ⁴)			Ibz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	4.1	7.51	30.791	67.24	0.4579	0.8	0.556669038				3514248952	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	4.1	7.51	30.791	67.24	0.4579	0.8	0.556669038				16895773126	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	4.1	7.51	30.791	67.24	0.4579	0.8	0.556669038				17314276993	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	4.1	7.51	30.791	67.24	0.4579	0.8	0.556669038	144.71796			50171946881	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	4.1	7.51	30.791	67.24	0.4579	0.8	0.556669038		43.133059		19453078571	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	4.1	7.51	30.791	67.24	0.4579	0.8	0.556669038			187.85102	2.76769E+11	krz

Point 8

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	Ibx(m ⁴)	Iby(m ⁴)			Ibz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	4.3	7.53	32.379	73.96	0.4378	0.8	0.538207688				3619659547	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	4.3	7.53	32.379	73.96	0.4378	0.8	0.538207688				17478826639	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	4.3	7.53	32.379	73.96	0.4378	0.8	0.538207688				17875239392	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	4.3	7.53	32.379	73.96	0.4378	0.8	0.538207688	152.9932			52257505096	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	4.3	7.53	32.379	73.96	0.4378	0.8	0.538207688		49.890643		21843609383	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	4.3	7.53	32.379	73.96	0.4378	0.8	0.538207688			202.88385	2.96683E+11	krz

Point 10

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	Ibx(m ⁴)	Iby(m ⁴)			Ibz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	11.2442	7.588	85.321	505.73	0.1687	0.8	0.26324133				6894011909	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	11.2442	7.588	85.321	505.73	0.1687	0.8	0.26324133				36314553669	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	11.2442	7.588	85.321	505.73	0.1687	0.8	0.26324133				35865834069	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	11.2442	7.588	85.321	505.73	0.1687	0.8	0.26324133	409.38251			1.15965E+11	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	11.2442	7.588	85.321	505.73	0.1687	0.8	0.26324133		898.94219		2.20408E+11	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	11.2442	7.588	85.321	505.73	0.1687	0.8	0.26324133			1308.3247	1.72265E+12	krz

Point 12

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	Ibx(m ⁴)	Iby(m ⁴)			Ibz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	7.7	7.62	58.674	237.16	0.2474	0.8	0.350794836				5281640381	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	7.7	7.62	58.674	237.16	0.2474	0.8	0.350794836				26915901373	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	7.7	7.62	58.674	237.16	0.2474	0.8	0.350794836				26906083101	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	7.7	7.62	58.674	237.16	0.2474	0.8	0.350794836	283.90588			84688000462	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	7.7	7.62	58.674	237.16	0.2474	0.8	0.350794836		289.89846		89058186190	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	7.7	7.62	58.674	237.16	0.2474	0.8	0.350794836			573.80434	7.76833E+11	krz

Point 14

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	Ibx(m ⁴)	Iby(m ⁴)			Ibz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	10.4	7.6	79.04	432.64	0.1827	0.8	0.279441045				6516525199	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	10.4	7.6	79.04	432.64	0.1827	0.8	0.279441045				34099857631	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	10.4	7.6	79.04	432.64	0.1827	0.8	0.279441045				33756218093	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	10.4	7.6	79.04	432.64	0.1827	0.8	0.279441045	380.44587			1.08697E+11	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	10.4	7.6	79.04	432.64	0.1827	0.8	0.279441045		712.41387		1.82933E+11	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	10.4	7.6	79.04	432.64	0.1827	0.8	0.279441045			1092.8597	1.44505E+12	krz

Point 2

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness										K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation		
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	Ibx(m ⁴)			Iby(m ⁴)	Ibz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	5.6	7.7	43.12	125.44	0.3438	0.8	0.448933516				4298225138	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	5.6	7.7	43.12	125.44	0.3438	0.8	0.448933516				21244555381	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	5.6	7.7	43.12	125.44	0.3438	0.8	0.448933516				21502285035	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	5.6	7.7	43.12	125.44	0.3438	0.8	0.448933516	213.04873			67077722957	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	5.6	7.7	43.12	125.44	0.3438	0.8	0.448933516		112.68693		41731963849	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	5.6	7.7	43.12	125.44	0.3438	0.8	0.448933516			325.73567	4.60114E+11	krz

Point 17

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness										K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation		
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	Ibx(m ⁴)			Iby(m ⁴)	Ibz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	4.5	4.826	21.717	81	0.2681	0.8	0.372594216				3168251347	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	4.5	4.826	21.717	81	0.2681	0.8	0.372594216				16028045270	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	4.5	4.826	21.717	81	0.2681	0.8	0.372594216				16068054731	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	4.5	4.826	21.717	81	0.2681	0.8	0.372594216	42.149577			20136219560	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	4.5	4.826	21.717	81	0.2681	0.8	0.372594216		36.647438		18654583035	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	4.5	4.826	21.717	81	0.2681	0.8	0.372594216			78.797014	98185432085	krz

Point 3

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	Ibx(m ⁴)	Iby(m ⁴)			Ibz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	10.069	4.77	48.029	405.54	0.1184	0.8	0.201884992				5659711923	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	10.069	4.77	48.029	405.54	0.1184	0.8	0.201884992				3064252294	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	10.069	4.77	48.029	405.54	0.1184	0.8	0.210884992				29992184468	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	10.069	4.77	48.029	405.54	0.1184	0.8	0.210884992	91.066833			39528739510	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	10.069	4.77	48.029	405.54	0.1184	0.8	0.210884992		405.78516		1.27997E+11	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	10.069	4.77	48.029	405.54	0.1184		0.210884992			496.85199	5.91306E+11	krz

Point 32

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	Ibx(m ⁴)	Iby(m ⁴)			Ibz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	5.59	4.75	26.553	124.99	0.2124	0.8	0.312907777				3658208658	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	5.59	4.75	26.553	124.99	0.2124	0.8	0.312907777				18896931298	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	5.59	4.75	26.553	124.99	0.2124	0.8	0.312907777				18793839437	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	5.59	4.75	26.553	124.99	0.2124	0.8	0.312907777	49.924232			23313029898	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	5.59	4.75	26.553	124.99	0.2124	0.8	0.312907777		69.142931		31097654007	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	5.59	4.75	26.553	124.99	0.2124	0.8	0.312907777			119.06716	1.44724E+11	krz

Point 5

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	Ibx(m ⁴)	Iby(m ⁴)			Ibz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	4.13	4.73	19.535	68.228	0.2863	0.8	0.391415774				2972394066	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	4.13	4.73	19.535	68.228	0.2863	0.8	0.391415774				14946300034	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	4.13	4.73	19.535	68.228	0.2863	0.8	0.391415774				15019937078	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	4.13	4.73	19.535	68.228	0.2863	0.8	0.391415774	36.42103			17972827464	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	4.13	4.73	19.535	68.228	0.2863	0.8	0.391415774		27.76707		15000990326	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	4.13	4.73	19.535	68.228	0.2863	0.8	0.391415774			64.1881	80267273591	krz

Point 7

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	Ibx(m ⁴)	Iby(m ⁴)			Ibz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	4.26	4.73	20.15	72.59	0.2776	0.8	0.382422699				3034096804	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	4.26	4.73	20.15	72.59	0.2776	0.8	0.382422699				15300395476	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	4.26	4.73	20.15	72.59	0.2776	0.8	0.382422699				15358077828	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	4.26	4.73	20.15	72.59	0.2776	0.8	0.382422699	37.567455			18429577661	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	4.26	4.73	20.15	72.59	0.2776	0.8	0.382422699		30.472543		16159311203	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	4.26	4.73	20.15	72.59	0.2776	0.8	0.382422699			68.039998	84773658688	krz

Point 9

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness										K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation		
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	Ibx(m ⁴)			Iby(m ⁴)	Ibz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	11.33	4.63	52.458	513.48	0.1022	0.8	0.180704229				6168943300	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	11.33	4.63	52.458	513.48	0.1022	0.8	0.180704229				33751125274	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	11.33	4.63	52.458	513.48	0.1022	0.8	0.180704229				32928844950	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	11.33	4.63	52.458	513.48	0.1022	0.8	0.180704229	93.71123			41389378639	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	11.33	4.63	52.458	513.48	0.1022	0.8	0.180704229		561.16358		1.66887E+11	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	11.33	4.63	52.458	513.48	0.1022	0.8	0.180704229			654.87481	7.74883E+11	krz

Point 11

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness										K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation		
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	Ibx(m ⁴)			Iby(m ⁴)	Ibz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	7.63	4.62	35.251	232.87	0.1514	0.8	0.242685084				4547651082	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	7.63	4.62	35.251	232.87	0.1514	0.8	0.242685084				24165623099	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	7.63	4.62	35.251	232.87	0.1514	0.8	0.242685084				23796210595	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	7.63	4.62	35.251	232.87	0.1514	0.8	0.242685084	62.700242			28801599133	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	7.63	4.62	35.251	232.87	0.1514	0.8	0.242685084		171.01505		64530822264	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	7.63	4.62	35.251	232.87	0.1514	0.8	0.242685084			233.7153	2.7754E+11	krz

Point 13

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness										K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation		
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	AL ² (m ²)	Ab/AL ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ³) ^{0.75}	Ibx(m ⁴)			Iby(m ⁴)	Ibz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	10.4	4.57	47.528	432.64	0.1099	0.8	0.190817039				5750040996	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	10.4	4.57	47.528	432.64	0.1099	0.8	0.190817039				31300199422	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	10.4	4.57	47.528	432.64	0.1099	0.8	0.190817039				30584692812	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	10.4	4.57	47.528	432.64	0.1099	0.8	0.190817039	82.718127			37232404158	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	10.4	4.57	47.528	432.64	0.1099	0.8	0.190817039		428.38571		1.3482E+11	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	10.4	4.57	47.528	432.64	0.1099	0.8	0.190817039			511.10383	6.03001E+11	krz

Point 430

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness										K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation		
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	AL ² (m ²)	Ab/AL ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ³) ^{0.75}	Ibx(m ⁴)			Iby(m ⁴)	Ibz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	5.6	4.54	25.424	125.44	0.2027	0.8	0.302068804				3614275727	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	5.6	4.54	25.424	125.44	0.2027	0.8	0.302068804				18746363541	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	5.6	4.54	25.424	125.44	0.2027	0.8	0.302068804				18616271430	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	5.6	4.54	25.424	125.44	0.2027	0.8	0.302068804	43.66911			21187989967	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	5.6	4.54	25.424	125.44	0.2027	0.8	0.302068804		66.441387		30395402525	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	5.6	4.54	25.424	125.44	0.2027	0.8	0.302068804			110.1105	1.32182E+11	krz

Point 16

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness										K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation		
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	Ibx(m ⁴)			Iby(m ⁴)	Ibz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	4.5	4.83	21.735	81	0.2683	0.8	0.372825809				3169118021	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	4.5	4.83	21.735	81	0.2683	0.8	0.372825809				16031210884	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	4.5	4.83	21.735	81	0.2683	0.8	0.272825809				16071711258	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	4.5	4.83	21.735	81	0.2683	0.8	0.272825809	42.25447			20172665948	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	4.5	4.83	21.735	81	0.2683	0.8	0.272825809		36.677813		18663858538	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	4.5	4.83	21.735	81	0.2683	0.8	0.272825809			78.932283	98379291330	krz

Point 20

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness										K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation		
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	Ibx(m ⁴)			Iby(m ⁴)	Ibz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	10.05	4.806	48.3	404.01	0.1196	0.8	0.203314468				5660979232	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	10.05	4.806	48.3	404.01	0.1196	0.8	0.203314468				30628338317	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	10.05	4.806	48.3	404.01	0.1196	0.8	0.203314468				29984750553	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	10.05	4.806	48.3	404.01	0.1196	0.8	0.203314468	92.968562			40085937599	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	10.05	4.806	48.3	404.01	0.1196	0.8	0.203314468		406.53759		1.27995E+11	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	10.05	4.806	48.3	404.01	0.1196	0.8	0.203314468			499.50615	5.9539E+11	krz

Point 18

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	AL ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	Ibx(m ⁴)	Iby(m ⁴)			Ibz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	4.5	7.412	33.354	81	0.4118	0.8	0.514040313				3697575818	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	4.5	7.412	33.354	81	0.4118	0.8	0.514040313				17961454461	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	4.5	7.412	33.354	81	0.4118	0.8	0.514040313				18318839581	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	4.5	7.412	33.354	81	0.4118	0.8	0.514040313	152.69946			52145923392	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	4.5	7.412	33.354	81	0.4118	0.8	0.514040313		56.284875		24132060310	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	4.5	7.412	33.354	81	0.4118	0.8	0.514040313			208.98433	3.01434E+11	krz

Point 22

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	AL ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	Ibx(m ⁴)	Iby(m ⁴)			Ibz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	5.6	4.76	26.656	125.44	0.2125	0.8	0.312981884				3665097975	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	5.6	4.76	26.656	125.44	0.2125	0.8	0.312981884				18931996753	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	5.6	4.76	26.656	125.44	0.2125	0.8	0.312981884				18828904891	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	5.6	4.76	26.656	125.44	0.2125	0.8	0.312981884	50.330082			23454287936	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	5.6	4.76	26.656	125.44	0.2125	0.8	0.312981884		69.661013		31270768829	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	5.6	4.76	26.656	125.44	0.2125	0.8	0.312981884			119.9911	1.45912E+11	krz

Point 24

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	Ibx(m ⁴)	Iby(m ⁴)			Ibz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	8.4	4.75	39.9	282.24	0.1414	0.8	0.230550331				4921820971	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	8.4	4.75	39.9	282.24	0.1414	0.8	0.230550331				26294734606	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	8.4	4.75	39.9	282.24	0.1414	0.8	0.230550331				25846775922	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	8.4	4.75	39.9	282.24	0.1414	0.8	0.230550331	75.020313			33269528767	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	8.4	4.75	39.9	282.24	0.1414	0.8	0.230550331		234.612		82643666199	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	8.4	4.75	39.9	282.24	0.1414	0.8	0.230550331			309.63231	3.69069E+11	krz

Point 26

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	Ibx(m ⁴)	Iby(m ⁴)			Ibz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	11.39	4.332	49.341	518.93	0.0951	0.8	0.171229485				6111867129	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	11.39	4.332	49.341	518.93	0.0951	0.8	0.171229485				33602058312	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	11.39	4.332	49.341	518.93	0.0951	0.8	0.171229485				32735841219	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	11.39	4.332	49.341	518.93	0.0951	0.8	0.171229485	77.162772			36226820769	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	11.39	4.332	49.341	518.93	0.0951	0.8	0.171229485		533.43115		1.62403E+11	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	11.39	4.332	49.341	518.93	0.0951	0.8	0.171229485			610.59392	7.13431E+11	krz

Point 28

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness										K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation		
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	Ibx(m ⁴)			Iby(m ⁴)	Ibz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	7.6	4.69	35.644	231.04	0.1543	0.8	0.246163946				4551757574	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	7.6	4.69	35.644	231.04	0.1543	0.8	0.246163946				24150917801	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	7.6	4.69	35.644	231.04	0.1543	0.8	0.246163946				23793778138	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	7.6	4.69	35.644	231.04	0.1543	0.8	0.246163946	65.335749			29627733165	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	7.6	4.69	35.644	231.04	0.1543	0.8	0.246163946		171.56645		64502931051	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	7.6	4.69	35.644	231.04	0.1543	0.8	0.246163946			236.9022	2.82342E+11	krz

Point 37

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness										K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation		
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	Ibx(m ⁴)			Iby(m ⁴)	Ibz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	4.8	3.49	16.752	92.16	0.1818	0.8	0.278383281				3003404721	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	4.8	3.49	16.752	92.16	0.1818	0.8	0.278383281				15722973489	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	4.8	3.49	16.752	92.16	0.1818	0.8	0.278383281				15562199276	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	4.8	3.49	16.752	92.16	0.1818	0.8	0.278383281	17.00342			10572068687	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	4.8	3.49	16.752	92.16	0.1818	0.8	0.278383281		32.16384		17930704296	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	4.8	3.49	16.752	92.16	0.1818	0.8	0.278383281			49.16726	55625860490	krz

Point 90

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness										K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation		
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	Ibx(m ⁴)			Iby(m ⁴)	Ibz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	1.2	3.49	4.188	5.76	0.7271	0.8	0.787386822				1258800687	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	1.2	3.49	4.188	5.76	0.7271	0.8	0.787386822				5786078422	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	1.2	3.49	4.188	5.76	0.7271	0.8					6067126473	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	1.2	3.49	4.188	5.76	0.7271	0.8		4.2508549			3686077473	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	1.2	3.49	4.188	5.76	0.7271	0.8			0.50256		643655329	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	1.2	3.49	4.188	5.76	0.7271	0.8			4.7534149		6595229565	krz

Point 77

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness										K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation		
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	Ibx(m ⁴)			Iby(m ⁴)	Ibz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	4.4	3.5	15.4	77.44	0.1989	0.8	0.297794404				2824147727	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	4.4	3.5	15.4	77.44	0.1989	0.8	0.297794404				14672157757	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	4.4	3.5	15.4	77.44	0.1989	0.8	0.297794404				14561702191	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	4.4	3.5	15.4	77.44	0.1989	0.8	0.297794404	15.720833			9867247222	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	4.4	3.5	15.4	77.44	0.1989	0.8	0.297794404		24.845333		14576403196	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	4.4	3.5	15.4	77.44	0.1989	0.8	0.297794404			40.566167	46169304184	krz

Point 92

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness										K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation		
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	Ibx(m ⁴)			Iby(m ⁴)	Ibz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	10.4	1.2	12.48	432.64	0.0288	0.8	0.069994826				4705083517	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	10.4	1.2	12.48	432.64	0.0288	0.8	0.069994826				27483390448	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	10.4	1.2	12.48	432.64	0.0288	0.8	0.069994826				26354289108	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	10.4	1.2	12.48	432.64	0.0288	0.8	0.069994826	1.4976			2408381095	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	10.4	1.2	12.48	432.64	0.0288	0.8	0.069994826		112.4864		60438250521	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	10.4	1.2	12.48	432.64	0.0288	0.8	0.069994826			113.984	1.07375E+11	krz

Point 80

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness										K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation		
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	Ibx(m ⁴)			Iby(m ⁴)	Ibz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	4.73	1.45	6.8585	89.492	0.0766	0.8	0.145658272				2437530670	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	4.73	1.45	6.8585	89.492	0.0766	0.8	0.145658272				13586752532	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	4.73	1.45	6.8585	89.492	0.0766	0.8	0.145658272				13184203359	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	4.73	1.45	6.8585	89.492	0.0766	0.8	0.145658272	1.2016664			1661486966	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	4.73	1.45	6.8585	89.492	0.0766	0.8	0.145658272		12.787045		10219053238	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	4.73	1.45	6.8585	89.492	0.0766	0.8	0.145658272			13.988711	13183955450	krz

Point 91

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	Ibx(m ⁴)	Iby(m ⁴)			Ibz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	10.4	1.2	12.48	432.64	0.0288	0.8	0.069994826				4705083517	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	10.4	1.2	12.48	432.64	0.0288	0.8	0.069994826				27482390448	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	10.4	1.2	12.48	432.64	0.0288	0.8	0.069994826				26354289108	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	10.4	1.2	12.48	432.64	0.0288	0.8	0.069994826	1.4976			2408381095	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	10.4	1.2	12.48	432.64	0.0288	0.8	0.069994826		112.4864		60438250521	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	10.4	1.2	12.48	432.64	0.0288	0.8	0.069994826			113.984	1.07375E+11	krz

Point 46

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	Ibx(m ⁴)	Iby(m ⁴)			Ibz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	4.7	1.5	7.05	88.36	0.0798	0.8	0.150123976				2439525099	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	4.7	1.5	7.05	88.36	0.0798	0.8	0.150123976				13564332722	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	4.7	1.5	7.05	88.36	0.0798	0.8	0.150123976				13171601821	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	4.7	1.5	7.05	88.36	0.0798	0.8	0.150123976	1.321875			1771128263	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	4.7	1.5	7.05	88.36	0.0798	0.8	0.150123976		12.977875		10271000185	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	4.7	1.5	7.05	88.36	0.0798	0.8	0.150123976			14.29975	13556088709	krz

Point 89

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	Ibx(m ⁴)	Iby(m ⁴)			Ibz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	1.4	1.5	2.1	7.84	0.2679	0.8	0.37232948				985369977.3	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	1.4	1.5	2.1	7.84	0.2679	0.8	0.37232948				4985377172	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	1.4	1.5	2.1	7.84	0.2679	0.8	0.37232948				4997650012	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	1.4	1.5	2.1	7.84	0.2679	0.8	0.37232948	0.39375			605098683.2	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	1.4	1.5	2.1	7.84	0.2679	0.8	0.37232948		0.343		561416488.7	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	1.4	1.5	2.1	7.84	0.2679	0.8	0.37232948			0.73675	726629098.6	krz

Point 48

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	Ibx(m ⁴)	Iby(m ⁴)			Ibz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	4.3	1.4	6.02	73.96	0.0814	0.8	0.152387622				2240000543	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	4.3	1.4	6.02	73.96	0.0814	0.8	0.152387622				12439487747	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	4.3	1.4	6.02	73.96	0.0814	0.8	0.152387622				12083575368	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	4.3	1.4	6.02	73.96	0.0814	0.8	0.152387622	0.9832667			1413316840	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	4.3	1.4	6.02	73.96	0.0814	0.8	0.152387622		9.2758167		7960204726	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	4.3	1.4	6.02	73.96	0.0814	0.8	0.152387622			10.259083	9588116289	krz

Point 93

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness										K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation		
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	Ibx(m ⁴)			Iby(m ⁴)	Ibz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	1.069	1.49	1.5928	4.571	0.3485	0.8	0.453535649				824591720.2	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	1.069	1.49	1.5928	4.571	0.3485	0.8	0.453535649				4070377539	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	1.069	1.49	1.5928	4.571	0.3485	0.8	0.453535649				4122046198	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	1.069	1.49	1.5928	4.571	0.3485	0.8	0.453535649	0.2946831			480929165.7	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	1.069	1.49	1.5928	4.571	0.3485	0.8	0.453535649		0.1516834		292672135.3	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	1.069	1.49	1.5928	4.571	0.3485	0.8	0.453535649			0.4463666	454883456.6	krz

Point 78

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness										K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation		
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	Ibx(m ⁴)			Iby(m ⁴)	Ibz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	4.6	1.48	6.808	84.64	0.0804	0.8	0.15103685				2391112414	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	4.6	1.48	6.808	84.64	0.0804	0.8	0.15103685				13288485151	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	4.6	1.48	6.808	84.64	0.0804	0.8	0.15103685				12905572522	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	4.6	1.48	6.808	84.64	0.0804	0.8	0.15103685	1.2426869			1688381517	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	4.6	1.48	6.808	84.64	0.0804	0.8	0.15103685		12.004773		9676068804	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	4.6	1.48	6.808	84.64	0.0804	0.8	0.15103685			13.24746	12522620531	krz

Point 15

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	Ibx(m ⁴)	Iby(m ⁴)			Ibz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	4.5	7.412	33.354	81	0.4118	0.8	0.514040313				3697575818	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	4.5	7.412	33.354	81	0.4118	0.8	0.514040313				17961454461	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	4.5	7.412	33.354	81	0.4118	0.8	0.514040313				18318839581	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	4.5	7.412	33.354	81	0.4118	0.8	0.514040313	152.69946			52145923392	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	4.5	7.412	33.354	81	0.4118	0.8	0.514040313		56.284875		24132060310	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	4.5	7.412	33.354	81	0.4118	0.8	0.514040313			208.98433	3.01434E+11	krz

Point 19

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	Ibx(m ⁴)	Iby(m ⁴)			Ibz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	10	7.44	74.4	400	0.186	0.8	0.283227036				6297374213	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	10	7.44	74.4	400	0.186	0.8	0.283227036				32903325208	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	10	7.44	74.4	400	0.186	0.8	0.283227036				32589140487	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	10	7.44	74.4	400	0.186	0.8	0.283227036	343.19232			1.00402E+11	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	10	7.44	74.4	400	0.186	0.8	0.283227036		620		1.64387E+11	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	10	7.44	74.4	400	0.186	0.8	0.283227036			963.19232	1.26945E+12	krz

Point 21

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	Ibx(m ⁴)	Iby(m ⁴)			Ibz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	5.6	7.412	41.507	125.44	0.3309	0.8	0.436280241				4239298795	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	4.5	7.412	33.354	81	0.4118	0.8	0.514040313				17961454461	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	4.5	7.412	33.354	81	0.4118	0.8	0.514040313				18318839581	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	4.5	7.412	33.354	81	0.4118	0.8	0.514040313	152.69946			52145923392	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	4.5	7.412	33.354	81	0.4118	0.8	0.514040313		56.284875		24132060310	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	4.5	7.412	33.354	81	0.4118	0.8	0.514040313			208.98433	3.01434E+11	krz

Point 23

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	Ibx(m ⁴)	Iby(m ⁴)			Ibz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	8.4	7.4	62.16	282.24	0.2202	0.8	0.321491379				5557090079	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	8.4	7.4	62.16	282.24	0.2202	0.8	0.321491379				28615116898	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	8.4	7.4	62.16	282.24	0.2202	0.8	0.321491379				28492388492	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	8.4	7.4	62.16	282.24	0.2202	0.8	0.321491379	283.6568			85494021615	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	8.4	7.4	62.16	282.24	0.2202	0.8	0.321491379		365.5008		1.07828E+11	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	8.4	7.4	62.16	282.24	0.2202	0.8	0.321491379			649.1576	8.64643E+11	krz

Point 25

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness										K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation		
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	Ibx(m ⁴)			Iby(m ⁴)	Ibz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	11.45	7.52	86.104	524.41	0.1642	0.8	0.257937373				6969687623	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	11.45	7.52	86.104	524.41	0.1642	0.8	0.257937373				36794740539	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	11.45	7.52	86.104	524.41	0.1642	0.8					36312417901	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	11.45	7.52	86.104	524.41	0.1642	0.8			405.76797		1.15598E+11	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	11.45	7.52	86.104	524.41	0.1642	0.8			940.70414		2.28974E+11	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	11.45	7.52	86.104	524.41	0.1642	0.8				1346.4721	1.76767E+12	krz

Point 27

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness										K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation		
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	Ibx(m ⁴)			Iby(m ⁴)	Ibz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	7.56	7.412	56.035	228.61	0.2451	0.8	0.348349521				5170236976	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	7.56	7.412	56.035	228.61	0.2451	0.8	0.348349521				26370367850	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	7.56	7.412	56.035	228.61	0.2451	0.8	0.348349521				26352204045	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	7.56	7.412	56.035	228.61	0.2451	0.8	0.348349521	256.53509			78546010348	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	7.56	7.412	56.035	228.61	0.2451	0.8	0.348349521		266.88216		83817881180	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	7.56	7.412								523.41726	7.04064E+11	krz

Point 39

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4I ² (m ²)	Ab/4I ²	1- μ	(Ab/4I ²) ^{0.75}	Ibx(m ⁴)	Iby(m ⁴)			Ibz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	10.4	3.5	36.4	432.64	0.0841	0.8	0.156217986				5450803482	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	10.4	3.5	36.4	432.64	0.0841	0.8	0.156217986				30207205254	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	10.4	3.5	36.4	432.64	0.0841	0.8	0.156217986				29360379249	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	10.4	3.5	36.4	432.64	0.0841	0.8	0.156217986	37.158333			21409762249	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	10.4	3.5	36.4	432.64	0.0841	0.8	0.156217986		328.08533		1.1488E+11	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	0.4	3.5	1.4	0.64	2.1875	0.8	1.798709574			1.4478333	2608243862	krz

Point 1

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4I ² (m ²)	Ab/4I ²	1- μ	(Ab/4I ²) ^{0.75}	Ibx(m ⁴)	Iby(m ⁴)			Ibz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	5.6	3.6	20.16	125.44	0.1607	0.8	0.25382878				3389621789	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	5.6	3.6	20.16	125.44	0.1607	0.8	0.25382878				17925793148	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	5.6	3.6	20.16	125.44	0.1607	0.8	0.25382878				17680336335	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	5.6	3.6	20.16	125.44	0.1607	0.8	0.25382878	21.7728			12923847847	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	5.6	3.6	20.16	125.44	0.1607	0.8	0.25382878		52.6848		26445749985	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	5.6	3.6	20.16	125.44	0.1607	0.8	0.25382878			74.4576	84288050937	krz

Point 53

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	AL ² (m ²)	Ab/AL ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ³) ^{0.75}	Ibx(m ⁴)	Iby(m ⁴)			Ibz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	5.6	4	22.4	125.44	0.1786	0.8	0.274700203				3486820068	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	5.6	4	22.4	125.44	0.1786	0.8	0.274700203				18280819333	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	5.6	4	22.4	125.44	0.1786	0.8	0.274700203				18084453882	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	5.6	4	22.4	125.44	0.1786	0.8	0.274700203	29.866667			16164755740	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	5.6	4	22.4	125.44	0.1786	0.8	0.274700203		58.538667		28171526625	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	5.6	4	22.4	125.44	0.1786	0.8	0.274700203			88.405333	1.02688E+11	krz

Point 38

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	AL ² (m ²)	Ab/AL ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ³) ^{0.75}	Ibx(m ⁴)	Iby(m ⁴)			Ibz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	5.6	4.6	25.76	125.44	0.2054	0.8	0.305057959				3628196231	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	5.6	4.6	25.76	125.44	0.2054	0.8	0.305057959				18797209536	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	5.6	4.6	25.76	125.44	0.2054	0.8	0.305057959				18674481130	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	5.6	4.6	25.76	125.44	0.2054	0.8	0.305057959	45.423467			21793262966	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	5.6	4.6	25.76	125.44	0.2054	0.8	0.305057959		67.319467		30635790177	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	5.6	4.6	25.76	125.44	0.2054	0.8	0.305057959			112.74293	1.35823E+11	krz

Point 18

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	Ibx(m ⁴)	Iby(m ⁴)			Ibz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	4.75	7.662	36.395	90.25	0.4033	0.8	0.5060476				3871424577	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	4.75	7.662	36.395	90.25	0.4033	0.8	0.5060476				18843992799	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	4.75	7.662	36.395	90.25	0.4033	0.8					19201377919	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	4.75	7.662				0.8		178.34166			58580146210	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	4.75	7.662				0.8		68.4292422			28028062307	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	4.75	7.662								246.48	3.56626E+11	krz

Point 4

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	Ibx(m ⁴)	Iby(m ⁴)			Ibz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	10.1	7.71	77.871	408.04	0.1908	0.8	0.2887385				6406640403	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	10.1	7.71	77.871	408.04	0.1908	0.8	0.2887385				33401446134	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	10.1	7.71	77.871	408.04	0.1908	0.8	0.2887385				33108125242	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	10.1	7.71	77.871	408.04	0.1908	0.8	0.2887385	385.74763			1.0928E+11	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	10.1	7.71	77.871	408.04	0.1908	0.8	0.2887385		661.968393		1.71999E+11	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	10.1	7.71	77.871	408.04	0.1908	0.8	0.2887385			1047.7	1.39283E+12	krz

Point 33

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	l _{bx} (m ⁴)	l _{by} (m ⁴)			l _{bz} (m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	5.6	7.74	43.344	125.44	0.3455	0.8	0.4506815				4306365385	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	5.6	7.74	43.344	125.44	0.3455	0.8	0.4506815				21274288426	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	5.6	7.74	43.344	125.44	0.3455	0.8	0.4506815				21536927216	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	5.6	7.74	43.344	125.44	0.3455	0.8	0.4506815	216.38625			67854844113	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	5.6	7.74	43.344	125.44	0.3455	0.8	0.4506815		113.27232		41861902688	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	5.6	7.74	43.344	125.44	0.3455	0.8	0.4506815			329.66	4.66492E+11	krz

Point 6

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	l _{bx} (m ⁴)	l _{by} (m ⁴)			l _{bz} (m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	4.1	7.76	31.816	67.24	0.4732	0.8	0.5705102				3561441621	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	4.1	7.76	31.816	67.24	0.4732	0.8	0.5705102				17068148946	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	4.1	7.76	31.816	67.24	0.4732	0.8	0.5705102				17517334914	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	4.1	7.76	31.816	67.24	0.4732	0.8	0.5705102	159.65693			54060420784	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	4.1	7.76	31.816	67.24	0.4732	0.8	0.5705102		44.5689133		19839074645	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	4.1	7.76	31.816	67.24	0.4732	0.8	0.5705102			204.23	3.04691E+11	krz

Point 8

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	l _{bx} (m ⁴)	l _{by} (m ⁴)			l _{bz} (m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	4.3	7.78	33.454	73.96	0.4523	0.8	0.5515544				3667386270	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	4.3	7.78	33.454	73.96	0.4523	0.8	0.5515544				17653153145	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	4.3	7.78	33.454	73.96	0.4523	0.8	0.5515544				18080248000	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	4.3	7.78	33.454	73.96	0.4523	0.8	0.5515544	168.74309			56280136199	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	4.3	7.78	33.454	73.96	0.4523	0.8	0.5515544		51.5470383		22275895617	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	4.3	7.78	33.454	73.96	0.4523	0.8	0.5515544			220.29	3.26139E+11	krz

Point 10

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	l _{bx} (m ⁴)	l _{by} (m ⁴)			l _{bz} (m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	11.24	7.833	88.076	505.728	0.1742	0.8	0.2695906				6953382047	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	11.24	7.833	88.076	505.728	0.1742	0.8	0.2695906				36531408882	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	11.24	7.833	88.076	505.728	0.1742	0.8	0.2695906				36112757742	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	11.24	7.833	88.076	505.728	0.1742	0.8	0.2695906	450.33085			1.24066E+11	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	11.24	7.833	88.076	505.728	0.1742	0.8	0.2695906		927.967072		2.24651E+11	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	11.24	7.833	88.076	505.728	0.1742	0.8	0.2695906			1378.3	1.82902E+12	krz

Point 12

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	l _{bx} (m ⁴)	l _{by} (m ⁴)			l _{bz} (m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	7.7	7.87	60.599	237.16	0.2555	0.8	0.3593917				5336689198	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	7.7	7.87	60.599	237.16	0.2555	0.8	0.3593917				27116972539	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	7.7	7.87	60.599	237.16	0.2555	0.8	0.3593917				27137836368	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	7.7	7.87	60.599	237.16	0.2555	0.8	0.3593917	312.77618			90842708799	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	7.7	7.87	60.599	237.16	0.2555	0.8	0.3593917		299.409559		90799969451	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	7.7	7.87	60.599	237.16	0.2555	0.8	0.3593917			612.19	8.36884E+11	krz

Point 14

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	l _{bx} (m ⁴)	l _{by} (m ⁴)			l _{bz} (m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	10.4	7.85	81.64	432.64	0.1887	0.8	0.2863072				6575908510	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	10.4	7.85	81.64	432.64	0.1887	0.8	0.2863072				34316760958	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	10.4	7.85	81.64	432.64	0.1887	0.8	0.2863072				34003803521	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	10.4	7.85	81.64	432.64	0.1887	0.8	0.2863072	419.23841			1.1647E+11	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	10.4	7.85	81.64	432.64	0.1887	0.8	0.2863072		735.848533		1.8652E+11	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	10.4	7.85	81.64	432.64	0.1887	0.8	0.2863072			1155.1	1.54007E+12	krz

Point 2

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	Ibx(m ⁴)	Iby(m ⁴)			Ibz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	5.85	7.95	46.508	136.89	0.3397	0.8	0.4450035				4470991165	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	5.85	7.95	46.508	136.89	0.3397	0.8	0.4450035				22123138937	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	5.85	7.95	46.508	136.89	0.3397	0.8	0.4450035				22380868590	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	5.85	7.95	46.508	136.89	0.3397	0.8	0.4450035	244.94919			74502422029	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	5.85	7.95	46.508	136.89	0.3397	0.8	0.4450035		132.633577		47240825541	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	5.85	7.95	46.508	136.89	0.3397	0.8	0.4450035			377.58	5.35855E+11	krz

Point 17

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	Ibx(m ⁴)	Iby(m ⁴)			Ibz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	4.75	4.826	22.924	90.25	0.254	0.8	0.3577876				3285777162	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	4.75	4.826	22.924	90.25	0.254	0.8	0.3577876				16704858573	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	4.75	4.826	22.924	90.25	0.254	0.8	0.3577876				16714185932	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	4.75	4.826	22.924	90.25	0.254	0.8	0.3577876	44.49122			21050601739	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	4.75	4.826	22.924	90.25	0.254	0.8	0.3577876		43.1009557		21239298873	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	4.75	4.826	22.924	90.25	0.254	0.8	0.3577876			87.592	1.08518E+11	krz

Point 3

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	l _{bx} (m ⁴)	l _{by} (m ⁴)			l _{bz} (m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	10.07	4.77	48.029	405.539	0.1184	0.8	0.201885				5659711923	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	10.07	4.77	48.029	405.539	0.1184	0.8	0.201885				3064252294	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	10.07	4.77	48.029	405.539	0.1184	0.8	0.201885				29992184468	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	10.07	4.77	48.029	405.539	0.1184	0.8	0.201885	91.066833			39528739510	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	10.07	4.77	48.029	405.539	0.1184	0.8	0.201885		405.785156		1.27997E+11	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	10.07	4.77	48.029	405.539	0.1184	0.8	0.201885			496.85	5.91306E+11	krz

Point 32

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	l _{bx} (m ⁴)	l _{by} (m ⁴)			l _{bz} (m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	5.59	4.75	26.553	124.992	0.2124	0.8	0.3129078				3658208658	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	5.59	4.75	26.553	124.992	0.2124	0.8	0.3129078				18896931298	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	5.59	4.75	26.553	124.992	0.2124	0.8	0.3129078				18793839437	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	5.59	4.75	26.553	124.992	0.2124	0.8	0.3129078	49.924232			23313029898	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	5.59	4.75	26.553	124.992	0.2124	0.8	0.3129078		69.1429313		31097654007	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	5.59	4.75	26.553	124.992	0.2124	0.8	0.3129078			119.07	1.44724E+11	krz

Point 5

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	l _{bx} (m ⁴)	l _{by} (m ⁴)			l _{bz} (m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	4.13	4.73	19.535	68.2276	0.2863	0.8	0.3914158				2972394066	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	4.13	4.73	19.535	68.2276	0.2863	0.8	0.3914158	0			14946300034	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	4.13	4.73	19.535	68.2276	0.2863	0.8	0.3914158	0			15019937078	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	4.13	4.73	19.535	68.2276	0.2863	0.8	0.3914158	36.42103			17972827464	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	4.13	4.73	19.535	68.2276	0.2863	0.8	0.3914158		27.7670697		15000990326	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	4.13	4.73	19.535	68.2276	0.2863	0.8	0.3914158			64.188	80267273591	krz

Point 7

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	l _{bx} (m ⁴)	l _{by} (m ⁴)			l _{bz} (m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	4.26	4.73	20.15	72.5904	0.2776	0.8	0.3824227				3034096804	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	4.26	4.73	20.15	72.5904	0.2776	0.8	0.3824227				15300395476	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	4.26	4.73	20.15	72.5904	0.2776	0.8	0.3824227				15358077828	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	4.26	4.73	20.15	72.5904	0.2776	0.8	0.3824227	37.567455			18429577661	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	4.26	4.73	20.15	72.5904	0.2776	0.8	0.3824227		30.4725425		16159311203	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	4.26	4.73	20.15	72.5904	0.2776	0.8	0.3824227			68.04	84773658688	krz

Point 9

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness										K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation		
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	Ibx(m ⁴)			Iby(m ⁴)	Ibz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	11.33	4.63	52.458	513.476	0.1022	0.8	0.1807042				6168943300	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	11.33	4.63	52.458	513.476	0.1022	0.8	0.1807042				33751125274	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	11.33	4.63	52.458	513.476	0.1022	0.8	0.1807042				32928844950	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	11.33	4.63	52.458	513.476	0.1022	0.8	0.1807042	93.71123			41389378639	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	11.33	4.63	52.458	513.476	0.1022	0.8	0.1807042		561.163577		1.66887E+11	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	11.33	4.63	52.458	513.476	0.1022	0.8	0.1807042			654.87	7.74883E+11	krz

Point 11

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness										K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation		
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	Ibx(m ⁴)			Iby(m ⁴)	Ibz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	7.63	4.62	35.251	232.868	0.1514	0.8	0.2426851				4547651082	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	7.63	4.62	35.251	232.868	0.1514	0.8	0.2426851				24165623099	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	7.63	4.62	35.251	232.868	0.1514	0.8	0.2426851				23796210595	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	7.63	4.62	35.251	232.868	0.1514	0.8	0.2426851	62.700242			28801599133	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	7.63	4.62	35.251	232.868	0.1514	0.8	0.2426851		171.015055		64530822264	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	7.63	4.62	35.251	232.868	0.1514	0.8	0.2426851			233.72	2.7754E+11	krz

Point 13

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	l _{bx} (m ⁴)	l _{by} (m ⁴)			l _{bz} (m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	10.4	4.57	47.528	432.64	0.1099	0.8	0.190817				5750040996	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	10.4	4.57	47.528	432.64	0.1099	0.8	0.190817				31300199422	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	10.4	4.57	47.528	432.64	0.1099	0.8	0.190817				30584692812	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	10.4	4.57	47.528	432.64	0.1099	0.8	0.190817	82.718127			37232404158	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	10.4	4.57	47.528	432.64	0.1099	0.8	0.190817		428.385707		1.3482E+11	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	10.4	4.57	47.528	432.64	0.1099	0.8	0.190817			511.1	6.03001E+11	krz

Point 430

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	l _{bx} (m ⁴)	l _{by} (m ⁴)			l _{bz} (m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	5.85	4.54	26.559	136.89	0.194	0.8	0.2923344				3728270613	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	5.85	4.54	26.559	136.89	0.194	0.8	0.2923344				19410279776	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	5.85	4.54	26.559	136.89	0.194	0.8	0.2923344				19249505564	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	5.85	4.54	26.559	136.89	0.194	0.8	0.2923344	45.618624			21997206643	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	5.85	4.54	26.559	136.89	0.194	0.8	0.2923344		75.7429481		33754424893	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	5.85	4.54	26.559	136.89	0.194	0.8	0.2923344			121.36	1.4527E+11	krz

Point 16

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	l _{bx} (m ⁴)	l _{by} (m ⁴)			l _{bz} (m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	4.75	4.83	22.943	90.25	0.2542	0.8	0.35801				3286655631	kk
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	4.75	4.83	22.943	90.25	0.2542	0.8	0.35801				16708067266	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	4.75	4.83	22.943	90.25	0.2542	0.8	0.35801				16717885538	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	4.75	4.83	22.943	90.25	0.2542	0.8	0.35801	44.601941			21088564516	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	4.75	4.83	22.943	90.25	0.2542	0.8	0.35801		43.1366797		21249859559	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	4.75	4.83	22.943	90.25	0.2542	0.8	0.35801			87.739	1.08727E+11	krz

Point 20

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	l _{bx} (m ⁴)	l _{by} (m ⁴)			l _{bz} (m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	10.05	4.806	48.3	404.01	0.1196	0.8	0.2033145				5660979232	kk
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	10.05	4.806	48.3	404.01	0.1196	0.8	0.2033145				30628338317	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	10.05	4.806	48.3	404.01	0.1196	0.8	0.2033145				29984750553	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	10.05	4.806	48.3	404.01	0.1196	0.8	0.2033145	92.968562			40085937599	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	10.05	4.806	48.3	404.01	0.1196	0.8	0.2033145		406.537588		1.27995E+11	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	10.05	4.806	48.3	404.01	0.1196	0.8	0.2033145			499.51	5.9539E+11	krz

Point 18

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	l _{bx} (m ⁴)	l _{by} (m ⁴)			l _{bz} (m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	4.5	7.412	33.354	81	0.4118	0.8	0.5140403				3697575818	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	4.5	7.412	33.354	81	0.4118	0.8	0.5140403	0			17961454461	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	4.5	7.412	33.354	81	0.4118	0.8	0.5140403	0			18318839581	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	4.5	7.412	33.354	81	0.4118	0.8	0.5140403	152.69946			52145923392	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	4.5	7.412	33.354	81	0.4118	0.8	0.5140403		56.284875		24132060310	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	4.5	7.412	33.354	81	0.4118	0.8	0.5140403			208.98	3.01434E+11	krz

Point 22

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	l _{bx} (m ⁴)	l _{by} (m ⁴)			l _{bz} (m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	5.6	4.76	26.656	125.44	0.2125	0.8	0.3129819				3665097975	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	5.6	4.76	26.656	125.44	0.2125	0.8	0.3129819				18931996753	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	5.6	4.76	26.656	125.44	0.2125	0.8	0.3129819				18828904891	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	5.6	4.76	26.656	125.44	0.2125	0.8	0.3129819	50.330082			23454287936	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	5.6	4.76	26.656	125.44	0.2125	0.8	0.3129819		69.6610133		31270768829	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	5.6	4.76	26.656	125.44	0.2125	0.8	0.3129819			119.99	1.45912E+11	krz

Point 24

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	l _{bx} (m ⁴)	l _{by} (m ⁴)			l _{bz} (m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	8.4	4.75	39.9	282.24	0.1414	0.8	0.2305503				4921820971	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	8.4	4.75	39.9	282.24	0.1414	0.8	0.2305503				26294734606	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	8.4	4.75	39.9	282.24	0.1414	0.8	0.2305503				25846775922	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	8.4	4.75	39.9	282.24	0.1414	0.8	0.2305503	75.020313			33269528767	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	8.4	4.75	39.9	282.24	0.1414	0.8	0.2305503		234.612		82643666199	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	8.4	4.75	39.9	282.24	0.1414	0.8	0.2305503			309.63	3.69069E+11	krz

Point 26

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	l _{bx} (m ⁴)	l _{by} (m ⁴)			l _{bz} (m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	11.39	4.332	49.341	518.928	0.0951	0.8	0.1712295				6111867129	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	11.39	4.332	49.341	518.928	0.0951	0.8	0.1712295				33602058312	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	11.39	4.332	49.341	518.928	0.0951	0.8	0.1712295				32735841219	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	11.39	4.332	49.341	518.928	0.0951	0.8	0.1712295	77.162772			36226820769	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	11.39	4.332	49.341	518.928	0.0951	0.8	0.1712295		533.431151		1.62403E+11	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	11.39	4.332	49.341	518.928	0.0951	0.8	0.1712295			610.59	7.13431E+11	krz

Point 28

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness										K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation		
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	Ibx(m ⁴)			Iby(m ⁴)	Ibz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	7.6	4.69	35,644	231.04	0.1543	0.8	0.2461639				4551757574	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	7.6	4.69	35,644	231.04	0.1543	0.8	0.2461639				24150917801	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	7.6	4.69	35,644	231.04	0.1543	0.8	0.2461639				23793778138	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	7.6	4.69	35,644	231.04	0.1543	0.8	0.2461639	65.335749			29627733165	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	7.6	4.69	35,644	231.04	0.1543	0.8	0.2461639		171.566453		64502931051	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	7.6	4.69	35,644	231.04	0.1543	0.8	0.2461639			236.9	2.82342E+11	krz

Point 37

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness										K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation		
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	Ibx(m ⁴)			Iby(m ⁴)	Ibz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	4.8	3.49	16,752	92.16	0.1818	0.8	0.2783833				3003404721	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	4.8	3.49	16,752	92.16	0.1818	0.8	0.2783833				15722973489	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	4.8	3.49	16,752	92.16	0.1818	0.8	0.2783833				15562199276	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	4.8	3.49	16,752	92.16	0.1818	0.8	0.2783833	17.00342			10572068687	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	4.8	3.49	16,752	92.16	0.1818	0.8	0.2783833		32.16384		17930704296	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	4.8	3.49	16,752	92.16	0.1818	0.8	0.2783833			49.167	55625860490	krz

Point 90

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	Ibx(m ⁴)	Iby(m ⁴)			Ibz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	1.2	3.49	4.188	5.76	0.7271	0.8	0.7873868				1258800687	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	1.2	3.49	4.188	5.76	0.7271	0.8	0.7873868				5786078422	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	1.2	3.49	4.188	5.76	0.7271	0.8	0.7873868				6067126473	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	1.2	3.49	4.188	5.76	0.7271	0.8	0.7873868	4.2508549			3686077473	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	1.2	3.49	4.188	5.76	0.7271	0.8	0.7873868		0.50256		643655329	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	1.2	3.49	4.188	5.76	0.7271	0.8	0.7873868			4.7534	6595229565	krz

Point 77

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	Ibx(m ⁴)	Iby(m ⁴)			Ibz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	4.4	3.5	15.4	77.44	0.1989	0.8	0.2977944				2824147727	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	4.4	3.5	15.4	77.44	0.1989	0.8	0.2977944				14672157757	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	4.4	3.5	15.4	77.44	0.1989	0.8	0.2977944				14561702191	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	4.4	3.5	15.4	77.44	0.1989	0.8	0.2977944	15.720833			9867247222	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	4.4	3.5	15.4	77.44	0.1989	0.8	0.2977944		24.8453333		14576403196	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	4.4	3.5	15.4	77.44	0.1989	0.8	0.2977944			40.566	46169304184	krz

Point 92

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	Ibx(m ⁴)	Iby(m ⁴)			Ibz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	10.4	1.2	12.48	432.64	0.0288	0.8	0.0699948				4705083517	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	10.4	1.2	12.48	432.64	0.0288	0.8	0.0699948				27483390448	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	10.4	1.2	12.48	432.64	0.0288	0.8	0.0699948				26354289108	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	10.4	1.2	12.48	432.64	0.0288	0.8	0.0699948	1.4976			2408381095	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	10.4	1.2	12.48	432.64	0.0288	0.8	0.0699948		112.4864		60438250521	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	10.4	1.2	12.48	432.64	0.0288	0.8	0.0699948			113.98	1.07375E+11	krz

Point 80

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	Ibx(m ⁴)	Iby(m ⁴)			Ibz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	4.73	1.45	6.8585	89.4916	0.0766	0.8	0.1456583				2437530670	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	4.73	1.45	6.8585	89.4916	0.0766	0.8	0.1456583				13586752532	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	4.73	1.45	6.8585	89.4916	0.0766	0.8	0.1456583				13184203359	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	4.73	1.45	6.8585	89.4916	0.0766	0.8	0.1456583	1.2016664			1661486966	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	4.73	1.45	6.8585	89.4916	0.0766	0.8	0.1456583		12.7870446		10219053238	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	4.73	1.45	6.8585	89.4916	0.0766	0.8	0.1456583			13.989	13183955450	krz

Point 91

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	l _{bx} (m ⁴)	l _{by} (m ⁴)			l _{bz} (m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	10.4	1.2	12.48	432.64	0.0288	0.8	0.0699948				4705083517	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	10.4	1.2	12.48	432.64	0.0288	0.8	0.0699948				27483390448	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	10.4	1.2	12.48	432.64	0.0288	0.8	0.0699948				26354289108	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	10.4	1.2	12.48	432.64	0.0288	0.8	0.0699948	1.4976			2408381095	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	10.4	1.2	12.48	432.64	0.0288	0.8	0.0699948		112.4864		60438250521	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	10.4	1.2	12.48	432.64	0.0288	0.8	0.0699948			113.98	1.07375E+11	krz

Point 46

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	l _{bx} (m ⁴)	l _{by} (m ⁴)			l _{bz} (m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	4.7	1.5	7.05	88.36	0.0798	0.8	0.150124				2439525099	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	4.7	1.5	7.05	88.36	0.0798	0.8	0.150124				13564332722	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	4.7	1.5	7.05	88.36	0.0798	0.8	0.150124				13171601821	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	4.7	1.5	7.05	88.36	0.0798	0.8	0.150124	1.321875			1771128263	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	4.7	1.5	7.05	88.36	0.0798	0.8	0.150124		12.977875		10271000185	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	4.7	1.5	7.05	88.36	0.0798	0.8	0.150124			14.3	13556088709	krz

Point 89

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	Ibx(m ⁴)	Iby(m ⁴)			Ibz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	1.4	1.5	2.1	7.84	0.2679	0.8	0.3723295				985369977.3	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	1.4	1.5	2.1	7.84	0.2679	0.8	0.3723295				4985377172	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	1.4	1.5	2.1	7.84	0.2679	0.8	0.3723295				4997650012	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	1.4	1.5	2.1	7.84	0.2679	0.8	0.3723295	0.39375			605098683.2	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	1.4	1.5	2.1	7.84	0.2679	0.8	0.3723295		0.343		561416488.7	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	1.4	1.5	2.1	7.84	0.2679	0.8	0.3723295			0.7368	726629098.6	krz

Point 48

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	Ibx(m ⁴)	Iby(m ⁴)			Ibz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	4.3	1.4	6.02	73.96	0.0814	0.8	0.1523876				2240000543	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	4.3	1.4	6.02	73.96	0.0814	0.8	0.1523876				12439487747	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	4.3	1.4	6.02	73.96	0.0814	0.8	0.1523876				12083575368	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	4.3	1.4	6.02	73.96	0.0814	0.8	0.1523876	0.9832667			1413316840	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	4.3	1.4	6.02	73.96	0.0814	0.8	0.1523876		9.27581667		7960204726	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	4.3	1.4	6.02	73.96	0.0814	0.8	0.1523876			10.259	9588116289	krz

Point 93

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	l _{bx} (m ⁴)	l _{by} (m ⁴)			l _{bz} (m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	1.069	1.49	1.5928	4.57104	0.3485	0.8	0.4535356				824591720.2	k _x
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	1.069	1.49	1.5928	4.57104	0.3485	0.8	0.4535356				4070377539	k _y
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	1.069	1.49	1.5928	4.57104	0.3485	0.8	0.4535356				4122046198	k _z
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	1.069	1.49	1.5928	4.57104	0.3485	0.8	0.4535356	0.2946831			480929165.7	k _{rx}
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	1.069	1.49	1.5928	4.57104	0.3485	0.8	0.4535356		0.15168343		292672135.3	k _{ry}
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	1.069	1.49	1.5928	4.57104	0.3485	0.8	0.4535356			0.4464	454883456.6	k _{rz}

Point 78

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	l _{bx} (m ⁴)	l _{by} (m ⁴)			l _{bz} (m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	4.6	1.48	6.808	84.64	0.0804	0.8	0.1510368				2391112414	k _x
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	4.6	1.48	6.808	84.64	0.0804	0.8	0.1510368				13288485151	k _y
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	4.6	1.48	6.808	84.64	0.0804	0.8	0.1510368				12905572522	k _z
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	4.6	1.48	6.808	84.64	0.0804	0.8	0.1510368	1.2426869			1688381517	k _{rx}
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	4.6	1.48	6.808	84.64	0.0804	0.8	0.1510368		12.0047733		9676068804	k _{ry}
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	4.6	1.48	6.808	84.64	0.0804	0.8	0.1510368			13.247	12522620531	k _{rz}

Point 15

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	Ibx(m ⁴)	Iby(m ⁴)			Ibz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	4.75	7.662	36.395	90.25	0.4033	0.8	0.5060476				3871424577	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	4.75	7.662	36.395	90.25	0.4033	0.8	0.5060476				18843992799	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	4.75	7.662	36.395	90.25	0.4033	0.8	0.5060476				19201377919	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	4.75	7.662	36.395	90.25	0.4033	0.8	0.5060476	178.0487			58507909543	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	4.75	7.662	36.395	90.25	0.4033	0.8	0.5060476		68.4292422		28028062307	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	4.75	7.662	36.395	90.25	0.4033	0.8	0.5060476			246.48	3.56626E+11	krz

Point 19

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	Ibx(m ⁴)	Iby(m ⁴)			Ibz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	10	7.69	76.9	400	0.1923	0.8	0.2903352				6356486630	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	10	7.69	76.9	400	0.1923	0.8	0.2903352				33119239067	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	10	7.69	76.9	400	0.1923	0.8	0.2903352				32835736448	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	10	7.69	76.9	400	0.1923	0.8	0.2903352	378.96384			1.07746E+11	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	10	7.69	76.9	400	0.1923	0.8	0.2903352		640.833333		1.67679E+11	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	10	7.69	76.9	400	0.1923	0.8	0.2903352			1019.8	1.35562E+12	krz

Point 21

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	Ibx(m ⁴)	Iby(m ⁴)			Ibz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	5.6	7.662	42.907	125.44	0.3421	0.8	0.4472709				4290482105	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	5.6	7.412	41.507	125.44	0.3309	0.8	0.4362802	0			21029321175	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	5.6	7.412	41.507	125.44	0.3309	0.8	0.4362802	0			21251705048	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	5.6	7.412	41.507	125.44	0.3309	0.8	0.4362802	190.02599			61636150729	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	5.6	7.412	41.507	125.44	0.3309	0.8	0.4362802		108.472149		40788302712	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	4.5	7.412	33.354	81	0.4118	0.8	0.5140403			208.98	3.01434E+11	krz

Point 23

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	Ibx(m ⁴)	Iby(m ⁴)			Ibz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	8.4	7.65	64.26	282.24	0.2277	0.8	0.3296034				5613756294	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	8.4	7.65	64.26	282.24	0.2277	0.8	0.3296034				28822095770	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	8.4	7.65	64.26	282.24	0.2277	0.8	0.3296034				28730049465	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	8.4	7.65	64.26	282.24	0.2277	0.8	0.3296034	313.38799			91846891183	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	8.4	7.65	64.26	282.24	0.2277	0.8	0.3296034		377.8488		1.09999E+11	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	8.4	7.65	64.26	282.24	0.2277	0.8	0.3296034			691.24	9.29405E+11	krz

Point 25

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	Ibx(m ⁴)	Iby(m ⁴)			Ibz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	11.45	7.77	88.967	524.41	0.1697	0.8	0.2643423				7030674700	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	11.45	7.77	88.967	524.41	0.1697	0.8	0.2643423				37017501777	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	11.45	7.77	88.967	524.41	0.1697	0.8	0.2643423				36565861241	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	11.45	7.77	88.967	524.41	0.1697	0.8	0.2643423	447.59713			1.23905E+11	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	11.45	7.77	88.967	524.41	0.1697	0.8	0.2643423		971.977547		2.33512E+11	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	11.45	7.77	88.967	524.41	0.1697	0.8	0.2643423			1419.6	1.87848E+12	krz

Point 27

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	Ibx(m ⁴)	Iby(m ⁴)			Ibz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	7.56	7.662	57.925	228.614	0.2534	0.8	0.357125				5225408098	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	7.56	7.662	57.925	228.614	0.2534	0.8	0.357125				26571885745	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	7.56	7.662	57.925	228.614	0.2534	0.8	0.357125				26584404043	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	7.56	7.662	57.925	228.614	0.2534	0.8	0.357125	283.37856			84414110184	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	7.56	7.662	57.925	228.614	0.2534	0.8	0.357125		275.883856		85502875476	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	7.56	7.662	57.925	228.614	0.2534	0.8	0.357125			559.26	7.59793E+11	krz

Point 39

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	Ibx(m ⁴)	Iby(m ⁴)			Ibz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	10.4	3.75	39	432.64	0.0901	0.8	0.1645142				5522555317	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	10.4	3.75	39	432.64	0.0901	0.8	0.1645142				30469285819	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	10.4	3.75	39	432.64	0.0901	0.8	0.1645142				29653141916	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	10.4	3.75	39	432.64	0.0901	0.8	0.1645142	45.703125			24692553473	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	10.4	3.75	39	432.64	0.0901	0.8	0.1645142		351.52		1.19735E+11	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	0.4	3.75	1.5	0.64	2.3438	0.8	1.8942333			1.7778	3302863959	krz

Point 1

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	Ibx(m ⁴)	Iby(m ⁴)			Ibz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	5.85	7.85	45.923	136.89	0.3355	0.8	0.4407987				4450535299	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	5.85	7.85	45.923	136.89	0.3355	0.8	0.4407987				22048421895	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	5.85	7.85	45.923	136.89	0.3355	0.8	0.4407987				22293878708	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	5.85	7.85	45.923	136.89	0.3355	0.8	0.4407987	235.8216			72438325563	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	5.85	7.85	45.923	136.89	0.3355	0.8	0.4407987		130.96523		46883388761	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	5.85	7.85	45.923	136.89	0.3355	0.8	0.4407987			366.79	5.18274E+11	krz

Point 38

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness										K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation		
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	Ibx(m ⁴)			Iby(m ⁴)	Ibz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	5.85	4.6	26.91	136.89	0.1966	0.8	0.2952273				3742343944	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	5.85	4.6	26.91	136.89	0.1966	0.8	0.2952273				19461683989	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	5.85	4.6	26.91	136.89	0.1966	0.8	0.2952273				19308273480	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	5.85	4.6	26.91	136.89	0.1966	0.8	0.2952273	47.4513			22624009966	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	5.85	4.6	26.91	136.89	0.1966	0.8	0.2952273		76.7439563		34021377993	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	5.85	4.6	26.91	136.89	0.1966	0.8	0.2952273			124.2	1.49178E+11	krz

Point 53

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness										K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation		
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	Ibx(m ⁴)			Iby(m ⁴)	Ibz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	6.1	4	24.4	148.84	0.1639	0.8	0.2576337				3711568076	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	6.1	4	24.4	148.84	0.1639	0.8	0.2576337				19596810947	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	6.1	4	24.4	148.84	0.1639	0.8	0.2576337				19339081293	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	6.1	4	24.4	148.84	0.1639	0.8	0.2576337	32.533333			17421083906	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	6.1	4	24.4	148.84	0.1639	0.8	0.2576337		75.6603333		34590012695	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	6.1	4	24.4	148.84	0.1639	0.8	0.2576337			108.19	1.25183E+11	krz

Point 18

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4I ² (m ²)	Ab/4I ²	1- μ	(Ab/4I ²) ^{0.75}	lbx(m ⁴)	lby(m ⁴)			lbz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	5.75	8.662	49.8065	132.25	0.376609	0.8	0.480748				4565486326	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	5.75	8.662	49.8065	132.25	0.376609	0.8	0.480748				22369276191	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	5.75	8.662	49.8065	132.25	0.376609	0.8					22726661311	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	5.75	8.662				0.8		311.42			89014341732	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	5.75	8.662				0.8		137.227			47719606905	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	5.75	8.662							448.643	6.57908E+11		krz

Point 4

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4I ² (m ²)	Ab/4I ²	1- μ	(Ab/4I ²) ^{0.75}	lbx(m ⁴)	lby(m ⁴)			lbz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	10.1	8.71	87.971	408.04	0.215594	0.8	0.316394				6638921205	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	10.1	8.71	87.971	408.04	0.215594	0.8	0.316394				34249874390	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	10.1	8.71	87.971	408.04	0.215594	0.8	0.316394				34079281905	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	10.1	8.71	87.971	408.04	0.215594	0.8	0.316394	556.15			1.41948E+11	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	10.1	8.71	87.971	408.04	0.215594	0.8	0.316394	747.827			1.85057E+11	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	10.1	8.71	87.971	408.04	0.215594	0.8	0.316394		1303.98	1.79134E+12		krz

Point 33

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m2)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	lbx(m ⁴)	lby(m ⁴)			lbz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	5.6	8.74	48.944	125.44	0.390179	0.8	0.493682				4506620379	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	5.6	8.74	48.944	125.44	0.390179	0.8	0.493682				22005739299	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	5.6	8.74	48.944	125.44	0.390179	0.8	0.493682				22391106495	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	5.6	8.74	48.944	125.44	0.390179	0.8	0.493682	311.56			89020217817	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	5.6	8.74	48.944	125.44	0.390179	0.8	0.493682		127.907		45027853764	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	5.6	8.74	48.944	125.44	0.390179	0.8	0.493682			439.467	6.49285E+11	krz

Point 6

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m2)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	lbx(m ⁴)	lby(m ⁴)			lbz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	4.1	8.76	35.916	67.24	0.534146	0.8	0.624806				3746568168	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	4.1	8.76	35.916	67.24	0.534146	0.8	0.624806				17744341691	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	4.1	8.76	35.916	67.24	0.534146	0.8	0.624806				18316256066	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	4.1	8.76	35.916	67.24	0.534146	0.8	0.624806	229.68			71401884892	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	4.1	8.76	35.916	67.24	0.534146	0.8	0.624806		50.3123		21335697360	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	4.1	8.76	35.916	67.24	0.534146	0.8	0.624806			279.988	4.37968E+11	krz

Point 8

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75} lbx(m ⁴)	lby(m ⁴)	lbz(m ⁴)			
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	4.3	8.78	37.754	73.96	0.510465	0.8	0.603913				3854616891	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	4.3	8.78	37.754	73.96	0.510465	0.8	0.603913	0			18337031224	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	4.3	8.78	37.754	73.96	0.510465	0.8	0.603913	0			18886854485	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	4.3	8.78	37.754	73.96	0.510465	0.8	0.603913	242.53			74199943127	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	4.3	8.78	37.754	73.96	0.510465	0.8	0.603913		58.1726		23952129194	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	4.3	8.78	37.754	73.96	0.510465	0.8	0.603913			300.706	4.66467E+11	krz

Point 10

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75} lbx(m ⁴)	lby(m ⁴)	lbz(m ⁴)			
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	11.2442	8.838	99.37624	505.7281	0.196501	0.8	0.295137				7192263459	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	11.2442	8.838	99.37624	505.7281	0.196501	0.8	0.295137				37403946505	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	11.2442	8.838	99.37624	505.7281	0.196501	0.8	0.295137				37108637414	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	11.2442	8.838	99.37624	505.7281	0.196501	0.8	0.295137	646.86			1.60513E+11	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	11.2442	8.838	99.37624	505.7281	0.196501	0.8	0.295137		1047.03		2.41526E+11	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	11.2442	8.838	99.37624	505.7281	0.196501	0.8	0.295137			1693.89	2.31842E+12	krz

Point 12

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4I ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75} lbx(m ⁴)	lby(m ⁴)	lbz(m ⁴)			
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	7.7	8.87	68.299	237.16	0.287987	0.8	0.393124				5552690762	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	7.7	8.87	68.299	237.16	0.287987	0.8	0.393124				27905939291	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	7.7	8.87	68.299	237.16	0.287987	0.8	0.393124				28049531526	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	7.7	8.87	68.299	237.16	0.287987	0.8	0.393124	447.8			1.17969E+11	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	7.7	8.87	68.299	237.16	0.287987	0.8	0.393124		337.454		97556235833	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	7.7	8.87	68.299	237.16	0.287987	0.8	0.393124			785.25	1.11432E+12	krz

Point 14

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4I ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75} lbx(m ⁴)	lby(m ⁴)	lbz(m ⁴)			
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	10.4	8.85	92.04	432.64	0.21274	0.8	0.313247				6808906773	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	10.4	8.85	92.04	432.64	0.21274	0.8	0.313247				35167809808	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	10.4	8.85	92.04	432.64	0.21274	0.8	0.313247				34977580777	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	10.4	8.85	92.04	432.64	0.21274	0.8	0.313247	600.73			1.50596E+11	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	10.4	8.85	92.04	432.64	0.21274	0.8	0.313247		829.587		2.00433E+11	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	10.4	8.85	92.04	432.64	0.21274	0.8	0.313247			1430.32	1.96916E+12	krz

Point 2

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4I ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75} lbx(m ⁴)	lby(m ⁴)	lbz(m ⁴)			
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	6.85	8.95	61.3075	187.69	0.326642	0.8	0.43207				5161588526	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	6.85	8.95	61.3075	187.69	0.326642	0.8	0.43207				25635768314	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	6.85	8.95	61.3075	187.69	0.326642	0.8	0.43207				25893497968	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	6.85	8.95	61.3075	187.69	0.326642	0.8	0.43207	409.24			1.09624E+11	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	6.85	8.95	61.3075	187.69	0.326642	0.8	0.43207		239.725		74075452882	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	6.85	8.95	61.3075	187.69	0.326642		0.43207			648.965	9.37831E+11	krz

Point 17

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4I ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75} lbx(m ⁴)	lby(m ⁴)	lbz(m ⁴)			
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	5.75	4.826	27.7495	132.25	0.209826	0.8	0.310023				3749123993	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	5.75	4.826	27.7495	132.25	0.209826	0.8	0.310023				19387433255	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	5.75	4.826	27.7495	132.25	0.209826	0.8	0.310023				19274032207	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	5.75	4.826	27.7495	132.25	0.209826	0.8	0.310023	53.858			24708130457	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	5.75	4.826	27.7495	132.25	0.209826	0.8	0.310023		76.4557		33595285825	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	5.75	4.826	27.7495	132.25	0.209826		0.310023			130.313	1.58751E+11	krz

Point 3

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4I ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75} lbx(m ⁴)	lby(m ⁴)	lbz(m ⁴)			
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	10.069	4.77	48.02913	405.539	0.118433	0.8	0.201885				5659711923	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	10.069	4.77	48.02913	405.539	0.118433	0.8	0.201885				30642522294	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	10.069	4.77	48.02913	405.539	0.118433	0.8	0.201885				29992184468	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	10.069	4.77	48.02913	405.539	0.118433	0.8	0.201885	91.067			39528739510	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	10.069	4.77	48.02913	405.539	0.118433	0.8	0.201885		405.785		1.27997E+11	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	10.069	4.77	48.02913	405.539	0.118433	0.8	0.201885			496.852	5.91306E+11	krz

Point 32

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4I ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75} lbx(m ⁴)	lby(m ⁴)	lbz(m ⁴)			
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	5.59	4.75	26.5525	124.9924	0.212433	0.8	0.312908				3658208658	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	5.59	4.75	26.5525	124.9924	0.212433	0.8	0.312908				18896931298	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	5.59	4.75	26.5525	124.9924	0.212433	0.8	0.312908				18793839437	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	5.59	4.75	26.5525	124.9924	0.212433	0.8	0.312908	49.924			23313029898	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	5.59	4.75	26.5525	124.9924	0.212433	0.8	0.312908		69.1429		31097654007	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	5.59	4.75	26.5525	124.9924	0.212433	0.8	0.312908			119.067	1.44724E+11	krz

Point 5

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	lbx(m ⁴)	lby(m ⁴)			lbz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	4.13	4.73	19.5349	68.2276	0.28632	0.8	0.391416				2972394066	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	4.13	4.73	19.5349	68.2276	0.28632	0.8	0.391416				14946300034	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	4.13	4.73	19.5349	68.2276	0.28632	0.8	0.391416				15019937078	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	4.13	4.73	19.5349	68.2276	0.28632	0.8	0.391416	36.421			17972827464	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	4.13	4.73	19.5349	68.2276	0.28632	0.8	0.391416	27.7671			15000990326	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	4.13	4.73	19.5349	68.2276	0.28632	0.8	0.391416		64.1881		80267273591	krz

Point 7

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	lbx(m ⁴)	lby(m ⁴)			lbz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	4.26	4.73	20.1498	72.5904	0.277582	0.8	0.382423				3034096804	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	4.26	4.73	20.1498	72.5904	0.277582	0.8	0.382423				15300395476	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	4.26	4.73	20.1498	72.5904	0.277582	0.8	0.382423				15358077828	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	4.26	4.73	20.1498	72.5904	0.277582	0.8	0.382423	37.567			18429577661	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	4.26	4.73	20.1498	72.5904	0.277582	0.8	0.382423	30.4725			16159311203	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	4.26	4.73	20.1498	72.5904	0.277582	0.8	0.382423		68.04		84773658688	krz

Point 9

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75} lbx(m ⁴)	lby(m ⁴)	lbz(m ⁴)			
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	11.33	4.63	52.4579	513.4756	0.102162	0.8	0.180704				6168943300	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	11.33	4.63	52.4579	513.4756	0.102162	0.8	0.180704				33751125274	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	11.33	4.63	52.4579	513.4756	0.102162	0.8	0.180704				32928844950	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	11.33	4.63	52.4579	513.4756	0.102162	0.8	0.180704	93.711			41389378639	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	11.33	4.63	52.4579	513.4756	0.102162	0.8	0.180704		561.164		1.66887E+11	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	11.33	4.63	52.4579	513.4756	0.102162	0.8	0.180704			654.875	7.74883E+11	krz

Point 11

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75} lbx(m ⁴)	lby(m ⁴)	lbz(m ⁴)			
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	7.63	4.62	35.2506	232.8676	0.151376	0.8	0.242685				4547651082	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	7.63	4.62	35.2506	232.8676	0.151376	0.8	0.242685				24165623099	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	7.63	4.62	35.2506	232.8676	0.151376	0.8	0.242685				23796210595	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	7.63	4.62	35.2506	232.8676	0.151376	0.8	0.242685	62.7			28801599133	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	7.63	4.62	35.2506	232.8676	0.151376	0.8	0.242685		171.015		64530822264	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	7.63	4.62	35.2506	232.8676	0.151376	0.8	0.242685			233.715	2.7754E+11	krz

Point 13

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4I ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75} lbx(m ⁴)	lby(m ⁴)	lbz(m ⁴)			
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	10.4	4.57	47.528	432.64	0.109856	0.8	0.190817				5750040996	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	10.4	4.57	47.528	432.64	0.109856	0.8	0.190817				31300199422	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	10.4	4.57	47.528	432.64	0.109856	0.8	0.190817				30584692812	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	10.4	4.57	47.528	432.64	0.109856	0.8	0.190817	82.718			37232404158	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	10.4	4.57	47.528	432.64	0.109856	0.8	0.190817		428.386		1.3482E+11	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	10.4	4.57	47.528	432.64	0.109856	0.8	0.190817			511.104	6.03001E+11	krz

Point 430

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4I ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75} lbx(m ⁴)	lby(m ⁴)	lbz(m ⁴)			
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	6.85	4.54	31.099	187.69	0.165693	0.8	0.259704				4179703182	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	6.85	4.54	31.099	187.69	0.165693	0.8	0.259704				22049336457	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	6.85	4.54	31.099	187.69	0.165693	0.8	0.259704				21765833838	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	6.85	4.54	31.099	187.69	0.165693	0.8	0.259704	53.417			25234073347	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	6.85	4.54	31.099	187.69	0.165693	0.8	0.259704		121.604		49296263896	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	6.85	4.54	31.099	187.69	0.165693	0.8	0.259704			175.02	2.07788E+11	krz

Point 16

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4I ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	lbx(m ⁴)	lby(m ⁴)			lbz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	6.25	4.83	30.1875	156.25	0.1932	0.8	0.291411				3978393335	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	6.25	4.83	30.1875	156.25	0.1932	0.8	0.291411	0			20719939484	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	6.25	4.83	30.1875	156.25	0.1932	0.8	0.291411	0			20545665147	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	6.25	4.83	30.1875	156.25	0.1932	0.8	0.291411	58.687			26583955920	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	6.25	4.83	30.1875	156.25	0.1932	0.8	0.291411		98.2666		41058534367	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	6.25	4.83	30.1875	156.25	0.1932	0.8	0.291411			156.953	1.90165E+11	krz

Point 20

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4I ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	lbx(m ⁴)	lby(m ⁴)			lbz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	10.05	4.806	48.3003	404.01	0.119552	0.8	0.203314				5660979232	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	10.05	4.806	48.3003	404.01	0.119552	0.8	0.203314				30628338317	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	10.05	4.806	48.3003	404.01	0.119552	0.8	0.203314				29984750553	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	10.05	4.806	48.3003	404.01	0.119552	0.8	0.203314	92.969			40085937599	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	10.05	4.806	48.3003	404.01	0.119552	0.8	0.203314		406.538		1.27995E+11	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	10.05	4.806	48.3003	404.01	0.119552	0.8	0.203314			499.506	5.9539E+11	krz

Point 18

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4I ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	lbx(m ²)	lby(m ²)			lbz(m ²)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	4.5	7.412	33.354	81	0.411778	0.8	0.51404				3697575818	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	4.5	7.412	33.354	81	0.411778	0.8	0.51404				17961454461	ky
											0					
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	4.5	7.412	33.354	81	0.411778	0.8	0.51404				18318839581	kz
											0					
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	4.5	7.412	33.354	81	0.411778	0.8	0.51404	152.7			52145923392	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	4.5	7.412	33.354	81	0.411778	0.8	0.51404	56.2849			24132060310	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	4.5	7.412	33.354	81	0.411778	0.8	0.51404		208.984		3.01434E+11	krz

Point 22

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4I ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	lbx(m ²)	lby(m ²)			lbz(m ²)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	5.6	4.76	26.656	125.44	0.2125	0.8	0.312982				3665097975	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	5.6	4.76	26.656	125.44	0.2125	0.8	0.312982				18931996753	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	5.6	4.76	26.656	125.44	0.2125	0.8	0.312982				18828904891	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	5.6	4.76	26.656	125.44	0.2125	0.8	0.312982	50.33			23454287936	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	5.6	4.76	26.656	125.44	0.2125	0.8	0.312982	69.661			31270768829	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	5.6	4.76	26.656	125.44	0.2125	0.8	0.312982		119.991		1.45912E+11	krz

Point 24

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	lbx(m ⁴)	lby(m ⁴)			lbz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	8.4	4.75	39.9	282.24	0.141369	0.8	0.23055				4921820971	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	8.4	4.75	39.9	282.24	0.141369	0.8	0.23055				26294734606	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	8.4	4.75	39.9	282.24	0.141369	0.8	0.23055				25846775922	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	8.4	4.75	39.9	282.24	0.141369	0.8	0.23055	75.02			33269528767	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	8.4	4.75	39.9	282.24	0.141369	0.8	0.23055		234.612		82643666199	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	8.4	4.75	39.9	282.24	0.141369	0.8	0.23055			309.632	3.69069E+11	krz

Point 26

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	lbx(m ⁴)	lby(m ⁴)			lbz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	11.39	4.332	49.34148	518.9284	0.095083	0.8	0.171229				6111867129	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	11.39	4.332	49.34148	518.9284	0.095083	0.8	0.171229				33602058312	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	11.39	4.332	49.34148	518.9284	0.095083	0.8	0.171229				32735841219	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	11.39	4.332	49.34148	518.9284	0.095083	0.8	0.171229	77.163			36226820769	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	11.39	4.332	49.34148	518.9284	0.095083	0.8	0.171229		533.431		1.62403E+11	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	11.39	4.332	49.34148	518.9284	0.095083	0.8	0.171229			610.594	7.13431E+11	krz

Point 28

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m2)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4I ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75} lbx(m ⁴)	lby(m ⁴)	lbz(m ⁴)			
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	7.6	4.69	35.644	231.04	0.154276	0.8	0.246164				4551757574	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	7.6	4.69	35.644	231.04	0.154276	0.8	0.246164				24150917801	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	7.6	4.69	35.644	231.04	0.154276	0.8	0.246164				23793778138	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	7.6	4.69	35.644	231.04	0.154276	0.8	0.246164	65.336			29627733165	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	7.6	4.69	35.644	231.04	0.154276	0.8	0.246164	171.566			64502931051	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	7.6	4.69	35.644	231.04	0.154276	0.8	0.246164		236.902	2.82342E+11		krz

Point 37

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m2)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4I ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75} lbx(m ⁴)	lby(m ⁴)	lbz(m ⁴)			
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	4.8	3.49	16.752	92.16	0.181771	0.8	0.278383				3003404721	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	4.8	3.49	16.752	92.16	0.181771	0.8	0.278383				15722973489	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	4.8	3.49	16.752	92.16	0.181771	0.8	0.278383				15562199276	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	4.8	3.49	16.752	92.16	0.181771	0.8	0.278383	17.003			10572068687	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	4.8	3.49	16.752	92.16	0.181771	0.8	0.278383	32.1638			17930704296	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	4.8	3.49	16.752	92.16	0.181771	0.8	0.278383		49.1673	55625860490		krz

Point 90

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75} lbx(m ⁴)	lby(m ⁴)	lbz(m ⁴)			
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	1.2	3.49	4.188	5.76	0.727083	0.8	0.787387				1258800687	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	1.2	3.49	4.188	5.76	0.727083	0.8	0.787387				5786078422	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	1.2	3.49	4.188	5.76	0.727083	0.8	0.787387				6067126473	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	1.2	3.49	4.188	5.76	0.727083	0.8	0.787387	4.2509			3686077473	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	1.2	3.49	4.188	5.76	0.727083	0.8	0.787387	0.50256			643655329	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	1.2	3.49	4.188	5.76	0.727083		0.787387		4.75341		6595229565	krz

Point 77

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75} lbx(m ⁴)	lby(m ⁴)	lbz(m ⁴)			
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	4.4	3.5	15.4	77.44	0.198864	0.8	0.297794				2824147727	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	4.4	3.5	15.4	77.44	0.198864	0.8	0.297794				14672157757	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	4.4	3.5	15.4	77.44	0.198864	0.8	0.297794				14561702191	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	4.4	3.5	15.4	77.44	0.198864	0.8	0.297794	15.721			9867247222	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	4.4	3.5	15.4	77.44	0.198864	0.8	0.297794	24.8453			14576403196	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	4.4	3.5	15.4	77.44	0.198864		0.297794		40.5662		46169304184	krz

Point 92

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4I ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75} lbx(m ⁴)	lby(m ⁴)	lbz(m ⁴)			
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	10.4	1.2	12.48	432.64	0.028846	0.8	0.069995				4705083517	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	10.4	1.2	12.48	432.64	0.028846	0.8	0.069995				27483390448	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	10.4	1.2	12.48	432.64	0.028846	0.8	0.069995				26354289108	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	10.4	1.2	12.48	432.64	0.028846	0.8	0.069995	1.4976			2408381095	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	10.4	1.2	12.48	432.64	0.028846	0.8	0.069995		112.486		60438250521	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	10.4	1.2	12.48	432.64	0.028846	0.8	0.069995			113.984	1.07375E+11	krz

Point 80

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4I ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75} lbx(m ⁴)	lby(m ⁴)	lbz(m ⁴)			
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	4.73	1.45	6.8585	89.4916	0.076638	0.8	0.145658				2437530670	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	4.73	1.45	6.8585	89.4916	0.076638	0.8	0.145658				13586752532	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	4.73	1.45	6.8585	89.4916	0.076638	0.8	0.145658				13184203359	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	4.73	1.45	6.8585	89.4916	0.076638	0.8	0.145658	1.2017			1661486966	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	4.73	1.45	6.8585	89.4916	0.076638	0.8	0.145658		12.787		10219053238	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	4.73	1.45	6.8585	89.4916	0.076638	0.8	0.145658			13.9887	13183955450	krz

Point 91

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	Ibx(m ⁴)	Iby(m ⁴)			Ibz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	10.4	1.2	12.48	432.64	0.028846	0.8	0.069995				4705083517	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	10.4	1.2	12.48	432.64	0.028846	0.8	0.069995				27483390448	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	10.4	1.2	12.48	432.64	0.028846	0.8	0.069995				26354289108	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	10.4	1.2	12.48	432.64	0.028846	0.8	0.069995	1.4976			2408381095	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	10.4	1.2	12.48	432.64	0.028846	0.8	0.069995		112.486		60438250521	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	10.4	1.2	12.48	432.64	0.028846	0.8	0.069995			113.984	1.07375E+11	krz

Point 46

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	Ibx(m ⁴)	Iby(m ⁴)			Ibz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	4.7	1.5	7.05	88.36	0.079787	0.8	0.150124				2439525099	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	4.7	1.5	7.05	88.36	0.079787	0.8	0.150124				13564332722	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	4.7	1.5	7.05	88.36	0.079787	0.8	0.150124				13171601821	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	4.7	1.5	7.05	88.36	0.079787	0.8	0.150124	1.3219			1771128263	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	4.7	1.5	7.05	88.36	0.079787	0.8	0.150124		12.9779		10271000185	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	4.7	1.5	7.05	88.36	0.079787	0.8	0.150124			14.2998	13556088709	krz

Point 89

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	lbx(m ⁴)	lby(m ⁴)			lbz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	1.4	1.5	2.1	7.84	0.267857	0.8	0.372329				985369977.3	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	1.4	1.5	2.1	7.84	0.267857	0.8	0.372329				4985377172	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	1.4	1.5	2.1	7.84	0.267857	0.8	0.372329				4997650012	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	1.4	1.5	2.1	7.84	0.267857	0.8	0.372329	0.3938			605098683.2	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	1.4	1.5	2.1	7.84	0.267857	0.8	0.372329		0.343		561416488.7	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	1.4	1.5	2.1	7.84	0.267857	0.8	0.372329			0.73675	726629098.6	krz

Point 48

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	lbx(m ⁴)	lby(m ⁴)			lbz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	4.3	1.4	6.02	73.96	0.081395	0.8	0.152388				224000543	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	4.3	1.4	6.02	73.96	0.081395	0.8	0.152388				12439487747	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	4.3	1.4	6.02	73.96	0.081395	0.8	0.152388				12083575368	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	4.3	1.4	6.02	73.96	0.081395	0.8	0.152388	0.9833			1413316840	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	4.3	1.4	6.02	73.96	0.081395	0.8	0.152388		9.27582		7960204726	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	4.3	1.4	6.02	73.96	0.081395	0.8	0.152388			10.2591	9588116289	krz

Point 93

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness										K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation		
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	l _{bx} (m ⁴)			l _{by} (m ⁴)	l _{bz} (m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	1.069	1.49	1.59281	4.571044	0.348457	0.8	0.453536				824591720.2	k _x
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	1.069	1.49	1.59281	4.571044	0.348457	0.8	0.453536				4070377539	k _y
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	1.069	1.49	1.59281	4.571044	0.348457	0.8	0.453536				4122046198	k _z
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	1.069	1.49	1.59281	4.571044	0.348457	0.8	0.453536	0.2947			480929165.7	k _{rx}
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	1.069	1.49	1.59281	4.571044	0.348457	0.8	0.453536		0.15168		292672135.3	k _{ry}
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	1.069	1.49	1.59281	4.571044	0.348457	0.8	0.453536		0.44637		454883456.6	k _{rz}

Point 78

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness										K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation		
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	l _{bx} (m ⁴)			l _{by} (m ⁴)	l _{bz} (m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	4.6	1.48	6.808	84.64	0.080435	0.8	0.151037				2391112414	k _x
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	4.6	1.48	6.808	84.64	0.080435	0.8	0.151037				13288485151	k _y
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	4.6	1.48	6.808	84.64	0.080435	0.8	0.151037				12905572522	k _z
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	4.6	1.48	6.808	84.64	0.080435	0.8	0.151037	1.2427			1688381517	k _{rx}
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	4.6	1.48	6.808	84.64	0.080435	0.8	0.151037		12.0048		9676068804	k _{ry}
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	4.6	1.48	6.808	84.64	0.080435	0.8	0.151037		13.2475		12522620531	k _{rz}

Point 15

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	lbx(m ⁴)	lby(m ⁴)			lbz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	5.75	8.662	49.8065	132.25	0.376609	0.8	0.480748				4565486326	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	5.75	8.662	49.8065	132.25	0.376609	0.8	0.480748				22369276191	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	5.75	8.662	49.8065	132.25	0.376609	0.8					22726661311	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	5.75	8.662				0.8		311.42			89014341732	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	5.75	8.662				0.8		137.227			47719606905	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	5.75	8.662								448.643	6.57908E+11	krz

Point 19

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	lbx(m ⁴)	lby(m ⁴)			lbz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	10	8.69	86.9	400	0.21725	0.8	0.318214				6588331878	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	10	8.69	86.9	400	0.21725	0.8	0.318214				33966076420	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	10	8.69	86.9	400	0.21725	0.8	0.318214				33805302207	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	10	8.69	86.9	400	0.21725	0.8	0.318214	546.86			1.40061E+11	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	10	8.69	86.9	400	0.21725	0.8	0.318214	724.167			1.80441E+11	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	10	8.69	86.9	400	0.21725	0.8	0.318214			1271.03	1.74632E+12	krz

Point 21

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4I ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75} lbx(m ⁴)	lby(m ⁴)	lbz(m ⁴)			
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	5.6	8.662	48.5072	125.44	0.386696	0.8	0.490374				4491214569	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	5.6	8.662	48.5072	125.44	0.386696	0.8	0.490374				21949468078	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	5.6	8.662	48.5072	125.44	0.386696	0.8	0.490374				22325262458	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	5.6	8.662	48.5072	125.44	0.386696	0.8	0.490374	303.29			87246917816	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	5.6	8.662	48.5072	125.44	0.386696	0.8	0.490374		126.765		44786311359	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	5.6	8.662	48.5072	125.44	0.386696	0.8	0.490374			430.058	6.33325E+11	krz

Point 23

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4I ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75} lbx(m ⁴)	lby(m ⁴)	lbz(m ⁴)			
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	8.4	8.65	72.66	282.24	0.25744	0.8	0.361416				5835985137	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	8.4	8.65	72.66	282.24	0.25744	0.8	0.361416				29633808266	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	8.4	8.65	72.66	282.24	0.25744	0.8	0.361416				29664490368	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	8.4	8.65	72.66	282.24	0.25744	0.8	0.361416	453.05			1.19877E+11	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	8.4	8.65	72.66	282.24	0.25744	0.8	0.361416		427.241		1.18414E+11	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	8.4	8.65	72.66	282.24	0.25744	0.8	0.361416			880.291	1.22731E+12	krz

Point 25

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75} lbx(m ⁴)	lby(m ⁴)	lbz(m ⁴)			
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	11.45	8.69	99.5005	524.41	0.189738	0.8	0.287485				7251040778	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	11.45	8.69	99.5005	524.41	0.189738	0.8	0.287485				37822410341	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	11.45	8.69	99.5005	524.41	0.189738	0.8	0.287485				37483679939	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	11.45	8.69	99.5005	524.41	0.189738	0.8	0.287485	626.16			1.57257E+11	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	11.45	8.69	99.5005	524.41	0.189738	0.8	0.287485		1087.06		2.49729E+11	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	11.45	8.69	99.5005	524.41	0.189738	0.8	0.287485			1713.22	2.3319E+12	krz

Point 27

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75} lbx(m ⁴)	lby(m ⁴)	lbz(m ⁴)			
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	7.56	8.662	65.48472	228.6144	0.286442	0.8	0.391541				5441780097	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	7.56	8.662	65.48472	228.6144	0.286442	0.8	0.391541				27362205546	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	7.56	8.662	65.48472	228.6144	0.286442	0.8	0.391541				27497452251	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	7.56	8.662	65.48472	228.6144	0.286442	0.8	0.391541	409.44			1.10341E+11	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	7.56	8.662	65.48472	228.6144	0.286442	0.8	0.391541		311.891		92033584982	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	7.56	8.662	65.48472	228.6144	0.286442	0.8	0.391541			721.335	1.01811E+12	krz

Point 39

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	lbx(m ⁴)	lby(m ⁴)			lbz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	10.4	4.75	49.4	432.64	0.114183	0.8	0.196427				5798556167	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	10.4	4.75	49.4	432.64	0.114183	0.8	0.196427				31477405808	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	10.4	4.75	49.4	432.64	0.114183	0.8	0.196427				30783990311	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	10.4	4.75	49.4	432.64	0.114183	0.8	0.196427	92.882			40356004830	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	10.4	4.75	49.4	432.64	0.114183	0.8	0.196427	445.259			1.37981E+11	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	0.4	4.75	1.9	0.64	2.96875	0.8	2.261675		3.59773	7429414247	krz	

Point 1

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	lbx(m ⁴)	lby(m ⁴)			lbz(m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	6.65	4.85	32.2525	176.89	0.182331	0.8	0.279026				4164522750	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	6.65	4.85	32.2525	176.89	0.182331	0.8	0.279026				21795857401	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	6.65	4.85	32.2525	176.89	0.182331	0.8	0.279026				21574946269	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	6.65	4.85	32.2525	176.89	0.182331	0.8	0.279026	63.222			28297559337	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	6.65	4.85	32.2525	176.89	0.182331	0.8	0.279026	118.857			47768336163	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	6.65	4.85	32.2525	176.89	0.182331	0.8	0.279026		182.079	2.20047E+11	krz	

point 38

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	l _{bx} (m ⁴)	l _{by} (m ⁴)			l _{bz} (m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	6.85	4.6	31.51	187.69	0.167883	0.8	0.262274				4194342828	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	6.85	4.6	31.51	187.69	0.167883	0.8	0.262274				22102809191	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	6.85	4.6	31.51	187.69	0.167883	0.8	0.262274				21826670276	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	6.85	4.6	31.51	187.69	0.167883	0.8	0.262274	55.563			25946997965	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	6.85	4.6	31.51	187.69	0.167883	0.8	0.262274		123.211		49686132499	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	6.85	4.6	31.51	187.69	0.167883	0.8	0.262274			178.773	2.12921E+11	krz

point 53

Sr.No.	Vibration mode	Direction	Static Spring Stiffness											K (N/m)	Spring Stiffness Notation	
			μ	G(N/m ²)	L(m)	B(m)	Ab(m ²)	4L ² (m ²)	Ab/4L ²	1- μ	(Ab/4L ²) ^{0.75}	l _{bx} (m ⁴)	l _{by} (m ⁴)			l _{bz} (m ⁴)
1)	Vertical	x	0.2	337503118	6.85	4	27.4	187.69	0.145985	0.8	0.236174				4045663077	kx
2)	Horizontal (lateral direction)	y	0.2	337503118	6.85	4	27.4	187.69	0.145985	0.8	0.236174				21559741919	ky
3)	Horizontal (longitudinal direction)	z	0.2	337503118	6.85	4	27.4	187.69	0.145985	0.8	0.236174				21209965960	kz
4)	Rocking (about longitudinal, x axis)	rx	0.2	337503118	6.85	4	27.4	187.69	0.145985	0.8	0.236174	36.533			19305576155	krx
5)	Rocking (about lateral, y axis)	ry	0.2	337503118	6.85	4	27.4	187.69	0.145985	0.8	0.236174		107.14		45689508790	kry
6)	torsion	rz	0.2	337503118	6.85	4	27.4	187.69	0.145985	0.8	0.236174			143.673	1.65597E+11	krz

The static spring stiffness formulae use the following parameters:

G = Shear modulus of soil

L =Length of the foundation

B= Breadth of the foundation

A =Area of the footing

μ = Poisson's ratio

Moment of inertia about x axis = I_{bx}

Moment of inertia about y axis = I_{by}

Moment of inertia about z axis = I_{bz}

Shear modulus calculation

The empirical formula for the calculation of shear modulus of a material on the basis of velocity of shear waves is as below:

$$G = \beta V_s^2$$

Where β = density of soil

V_s =Velocity of waves through soil

The type of soil for the foundation to rest on is rocky soil. The type of soil with the assumed bearing capacity of 1000 KN/m² is Residual deposits of shattered and broken rock and hard shale, Cemented materials. The type of soil can be classified as gravelly soils. Mass density of gravelly soils is found to be 2150 kg /m³.(26)

From Borcherdt (27) (1994) for top 30 m /s of the range 375 m/s to 700 m/s.

$$= 2150 \times 450^2$$

$$= 4353750 \text{ Kn/m}^2$$

3.3.2 SSI Analysis on Etaabs

- 1) The static springs are assigned at the foundation level of each of the multi-risers to account for the reduced stiffness of the building due to the SSI.
- 2) The assignment of springs is done in the following steps

Step A – Select the points on the base

Step B – Go to assign → Joint /Point → Point springs

Step C- Type the calculated static spring values as shown in the tables given as follows:

Fig 3.28: Selection of Spring properties from assign dialog box

Fig 3.29: Typing in the calculated spring values

CHAPTER 4

Results and discussions

4.1 Introduction

Three models are considered with varying heights in the range of G + 20, G + 30 and G + 50. They are analysed for the Soil Structure Interaction effects. This chapter presents the results from the analysis. The results presented here are focussed on following parameters:

1. Comparison of forces i.e. Shear forces and Bending Moments of the fixed base and the one with soil structure interaction effects considered.
2. Comparison of Quantity of steel of the fixed base and the one with soil structure interaction effect.
3. Comparisons of the storey shears.

4.2 Design of members:

Limit State Method of Design is the method used for the design of structural members. The Limit State Method uses the philosophy of limit states for deflection, serviceability, cracking etc. The straining is limited to 0.0035 in flexure and 0.002 in compression. The stress distribution diagrams across the beam and column members are as shown below:

Stress and strain distribution across the beam as per LSM

Fig 4.1 Stress and strain distribution across the RCC section

Stress and Strain distribution across the column as per LSM

Fig 4.2 Stress and strain distribution across the column section

4.3 Steel Quantity Calculations:

Area of steel for a balanced section which is a section such that the maximum permissible strain in extreme fibre of the concrete section and steel is reached simultaneously is given by:

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$$\frac{x}{d-d'} = \frac{0.0035}{\frac{0.87f_y}{2 \times 10^5} + 0.002} \text{----- (-A)}$$

Where d = depth of the section

d' = Cover to the section

f_y = Yield stress

Substitute equation (A) in the below equation:

$$M = 0.87f_y A_{st} * (d - (0.42X))$$

Refer Fig 4.2

4.4 Comparison of the results of fixed base and SSI (Soil Structure Interaction) models for G+20, G+30 and G+ 50

A) G+20

Fig 4.3 Diagram for Beam B17 at storey 2 for G + 20 for SSI model for the ADLWX combo

The Analysis results are given as below:

Shear force = 173.23 Kn at 8.380m

Moment = -376.970 Knm

Diagram for Beam B17 at Story 2 (W27X102)

Fig: 4.4 Diagram for Beam B17 at story 2 for G + 20 for fixed base case for ADLWX combo

The analysis results are given below:

Shear Force is 172.67Kn at 8.380m

Moment is -374.433Knm at 8.380m

Comparison of results:

a)The shear force in the fixed model is less than the SSI by 0.56 Kn

b)The moment in the fixed model is less than the SSI by 2.537 Knm

Moment diagram for B17 for the load case ADLXP for the cases:

a)SSI

Fig 4.5: Moment diagram fo beam B17 for G + 20 for the load case ADLXP for SSI Case

b)Fixed Base

Moment 3-3 Diagram

BEAM **B17**

Story Level **2**

END-I

END-J

distance

value

143.78

Move cursor over diagram for values

Fig 4.6 : Moment diagram fo beam B17 for G + 20 for the load case ADLXP for Fixed Base Case

+

Shear force diagram for cases:

a) SSI

Fig 4.7: Shear force Diagram for beam B17 for G + 20 at a distance of 5m from left end for the SSI case

b)Fixed Base

Fig 4.8: Shear force Diagram for beam B17 for G + 20 at a distance of 5m from left end for the Fixed Base case

Analysis results are given as below:

Shear force values at distance 5m from the left most end:

A)SSI case: 95.92 Knm

B)Fixed base:129.49 Knm

Bending Moment Diagram values at distance 5m from the left most end:

A)SSI case: 129.49Knm

B)Fixed base:143.78Knm

Comparison of results:

a)The shear force in the fixed model is less than the SSI by 33.57 Kn.

b)The moment in the fixed model is less than the SSI by 29.51Knm.

B)G+30

a)Diagram for Beam B17 at storey 2 for fixed base for the load case ADLWX

Diagram for Beam B17 at Story 2 (W27X102)

Fig 4.9: Diagram for Beam B17 for G + 30 for load case ADLWX for fixed base

The analysis results are given as below:

Shear force at distace 8.380m =198.92Kn

Bending Moment at distance of 8.380m = -477.523Knm

Diagram for Beam B17 at story 2 for SSI for load case ADLWX

Diagram for Beam B17 at Story 2 (W27X102)

Fig 4.10: Diagram for Beam B17 for G + 30 for load case ADLWX for SSI

The analysis results are given as below:

Shear force at distace 8.380m =200.70Kn

Bending Moment at distance of 8.380m = -484.870Knm

The comparison of results for the load case ADLWX shows that:

- 1)The Moment for SSI case is greater than the fixed by the 1.78Kn.
- 2) The Shear for SSI case is less than the fixed by the 7.347Knm.

b) Shear force diagram for fixed base case for the load case ADLXP:

Fig 4.11: Shear force diagram for Beam B17 for G + 30 for the load case ADLXP for fixed base case

Shear force diagram for SSI case for the load case ADLXP :

Shear Force 2-2 Diagram

Fig 4.12: Shear force diagram for Beam B17 for G + 30 for the load case ADLXP for SSI case

d) Bending Moment diagram of Beam B 17 for the load case ADLXP for the fixed base case:

Moment 3-3 Diagram

BEAM **B17**
Story Level **2**

END-I END-J
distance value **129.44**

Move cursor over diagram for values

Fig 4.13: Bending Moment diagram for Beam B17 for G +30 for the load case ADLXP for fixed base case

Bending Moment diagram of Beam B 17 for the load case ADLXP for the SSI case:

Fig 4.14: Bending Moment diagram for Beam B17 for G +30 for the load case ADLXP for SSI case

Analysis results are given as below:

Shear force values at distance 5m from the left most end:

A)SSI case: 109.85Kn

B)Fixed base:107.92Kn

Bending Moment Diagram values at distance 5m from the left most end:

A)SSI case: 129.68 Knm

B)Fixed base: 129.44Knm

Comparison of results:

a)The shear force in the fixed model is less than the SSI by 1.93Knm

b)The moment in the fixed model is less than the SSI by 0.24 Knm

C) G+50

a) Diagram for Beam B17 at story 2 for the load case ADLWX for the fixed base case:

Fig 4.15: Bending Moment diagram for Beam B17 for G +50 for the load case ADLWX forFixed Base case

The analysis results are given as below:

Shear force at distace 8.380m =315.46Kn

Bending Moment at distance of 8.380m = 936.201Knm

Diagram for Beam B17 at the story 2 for the load case ADLWX for the SSI case:

Diagram for Beam B17 at Story 2 (W27X102)

Fig 4.16: Bending Moment diagram for Beam B17 for G +50 for the load case ADLWX for SSI case

The analysis results are given as below:

Shear force at distance 8.380m = 315.41Kn

Bending Moment at distance of 8.380m = 935.939Knm

The comparison of results for the load case ADLWX shows that:

- 1) The Moment for SSI case is greater than the fixed by the 0.262 Knm
- 2) The Shear for SSI case is greater than the fixed by the 0.05 Kn

(b) Bending Moment diagram for beam B17 for the load case ADLXP for the fixed base case:

Fig 4.17: Bending Moment diagram for Beam B17 for G+50 for the load case ADLWX for Fixed Base case

Bending Moment Diagram for the beam B17 for the load case ADLXP for SSI case:

Moment 3-3 Diagram

BEAM **B17**

Story Level **2**

END-I

END-J

distance

value

155.87

Move cursor over diagram for values

Fig 4.18: Bending Moment Diagram for the beam B17 for the load case ADLXP for SSI case

c) Shear Force diagram for the beam B17 for G +50 for the load case ADXP for fixed base case:

Fig 4.19: Shear Force diagram for the beam B17 for G + 50 for the load case ADXP for fixed base case

Shear force diagram for beam B17 for the load case ADLXP for the SSI case:

Shear Force 2-2 Diagram

BEAM **B17**

Story Level **2**

END-I

END-J

distance

value

232.75

Move cursor over diagram for values

Fig 4.20: Shear force diagram for beam B17 for G + 50 for the load case ADLXP for the SSI case

Analysis results are given as below:

Shear force values at distance 5m from the left most end:

A)SSI case: 232.75Kn

B)Fixed base:232.81Kn

Bending Moment Diagram values at distance 5m from the left most end:

A)SSI case: 155.87Knm

B)Fixed base:155.85Knm

Comparison of results:

a)The shear force in the fixed model is greater than the SSI by 0.06Kn

b)The moment in the fixed model is less than the SSI by 0.02Knm

Observations:

1)The difference between the shear force and bending moment results between the fixed and SSI model is found to be decreasing with increasing storey height.

2)The difference in the analysis results is found to be maximum for G+20 for the ADLWX case as compared to G+50.

3)Considerable difference is found in the analysis results for the earthquake load case .Hence concluding the necessity of SSI model for low rise buildings.

4)It is observed that the values of the analysis results for the earthquake load case drop for the SSI effect in G+20 as compared to G+30,G+50.

The analysis results are given in the following units:

a) Length = mm

b) Section properties:

b = mm

D = mm

Cover = mm

D = mm

c) Material properties:

$f_{ck} = \text{N/mm}^2$

$f_y = \text{N/mm}^2$

d) $A_{st} = \text{mm}^2$

τ (Shear resistance) = N/mm^2

$V_{\max} = \text{Shear resistance of section} = \text{N}$

Shear reinforcement = mm^2

e) M = moment = Hogging = Sagging = Nmm

The following tables show the steel quantity calculation for flexure and shear for the cases of fixed base and SSI.

The following assumptions have been made to simplify the design calculations.

- a) The flexural reinforcement given for hogging and sagging is calculated for the maximum moment and assumed to be distributed throughout the span.
- b) The shear reinforcement is also given for the max shear across the span.
- c) The shear reinforcement is calculated in excess of the shear strength of the section accounting for the shear strength calculated from the percentage steel reinforcement.

Steel quantity Estimation of G+20 with fixed base

S.No	storey	Combination	Load	beam	length (mm)	Section Properties					Material properties				Pt%	t	Shear resistance of section						
						id	b	D	cover	d	fck	fy	Moment				Ast	N/mm2	N	Vmax	Vs	spacing	Shear rt.
													Sagging	Hogging									
1	3	CDWX	B17	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	8.8E+07	3.1E+08	470.51	2148.1	0.3686	0.36	49680	123365	73685.2	426.9529	3081.511		
2	3	CDWX	B18	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	1.5E+08	3E+08	856.5	2005.5	0.671	0.49	67620	187824	120204	261.7215	5026.947		
3	3	CDWX	B19	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	1.7E+08	2.6E+08	993.84	1642.2	0.7786	0.57	78660	140319	61658.8	510.2286	2578.57		
4	3	CDWX	B20	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	9.3E+07	2.8E+08	495.22	1863.5	0.388	0.36	49680	114485	64805.5	485.4544	2710.162		
5	3	CDWX	B21	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	7.5E+07	4.2E+07	393.11	214.7	0.308	0.36	49680	51655	1975.24	15927.22	82.60447		
6	3	CDWX	B22	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	7E+07	2.1E+08	368.53	1223.1	0.2887	0.36	49680	96238	46558.3	675.7135	1947.068		
7	3	CDWX	B23	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	1.9E+08	1.8E+08	1077.2	1058	0.8439	0.57	78660	113674	35013.8	898.5065	1464.274		
8	3	CDWX	B24	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	1.2E+08	2.1E+08	676.52	1253.4	0.53	0.49	67620	127693	60072.9	523.6987	2512.246		
9	3	CDWX	B25	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	1.1E+08	1.6E+08	582.17	878.56	0.4561	0.36	49680	134977	85296.9	368.8305	3567.113		
10	3	CDWX	B26	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	1.1E+08	1.5E+08	582.17	856.35	0.4561	0.36	49680	66525	16844.6	1867.663	704.4419		
11	3	CDWX	B27	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	1.5E+08	1.5E+08	852	852	0.6674	0.49	67620	103824	36204	868.9673	1514.05		
12	3	CDWX	B28	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	4.5E+07	1.3E+08	229.11	745.93	0.1795	0.29	40020	69014	28994.4	1085.041	1212.544		
13	3	CDWX	B29	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	8.5E+07	2.8E+08	448.02	1802.7	0.351	0.36	49680	123365	73685.2	426.9529	3081.511		
14	3	CDWX	B51	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	1.3E+08	2.7E+08	736.23	1771.8	0.5768	0.49	0.36	119328	119328	263.6436	4990.298		
15	3	CDWX	B31	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	1.2E+08	1.9E+08	666.87	1107.6	0.5224	0.49	67620	122922	55302.3	568.8754	2312.738		
16	3	CDWX	B32	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	8.7E+07	1.9E+08	461	1123.1	0.3611	0.36	49680	104969	55289.4	569.008	2312.2		
17	3	CDWX	B33	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	8.7E+07	2E+08	462.1	1150.3	0.362	0.36	49680	151105	101425	310.1823	4241.57		
18	3	CDWX	B34	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	9.9E+07	1.7E+08	529.68	958.04	0.4149	0.36	49680	103566	53885.5	583.8322	2253.49		
19	3	CDWX	B35	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	9.5E+07	7.8E+07	508.59	411.31	0.3984	0.36	49680	67593	17912.6	1756.307	749.106		
20	3	CDWX	B42	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	8.2E+07	3.7E+08	433.86	2994.6	0.3399	0.36	49680	114545	64864.9	485.0095	2712.648		
21	3	CDWX	B60	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	1E+08	2.3E+08	534.09	1426.9	0.4184	0.36	49680	135859	86179.1	365.0549	3604.006		
22	3	CDWX	B54	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	9.2E+07	2.3E+08	1424.9	1424.9	1.1162	0.64	88320	135208	46887.6	670.9684	1960.837		
23	3	CDWX	B36	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	8.7E+07	2.2E+08	461.07	1335.7	0.3612	0.36	49680	102288	52608.3	598.0065	2200.077		
24	3	CDWX	B37	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	8.2E+07	2.5E+08	432.29	1590.9	0.3387	0.36	49680	107232	57552.5	546.6332	2406.842		
25	3	CDWX	B38	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	8.2E+07	2.5E+08	434.7	1604.4	0.3405	0.36	49680	107587	57906.9	543.2876	2421.664		
26	3	CDWX	B39	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	8.3E+07	3.3E+08	437.59	2355.2	0.3428	0.36	49680	120143	70463.5	446.4738	2946.78		
27	3	CDWX	B40	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	1.4E+08	2.4E+08	748.91	1466	0.5867	0.49	67620	85457	17836.5	1763.801	745.9231		
28	3	CDWX	B10	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	1E+08	1E+08	547.5	542.09	0.4289	0.36	49680	80400	30720.1	1024.089	1284.712		
29	3	CDWX	B9	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	8.1E+07	8.1E+07	425.91	425.91	0.3337	0.36	49680	45356	-4323.9	-7275.81	-180.827		
30	3	CDWX	B8	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	1.1E+08	1E+08	599.95	550.18	0.47	0.36	49680	82750	33069.8	951.3245	1382.977		
31	3	CDWX	B2	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	1.6E+08	1.4E+08	916.62	783.44	0.7181	0.49	67620	110770	43150.3	729.0816	1804.544		
32	3	CDWX	B11	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	1.3E+08	2E+08	729.35	1179.2	0.5714	0.49	67620	117429	49808.9	631.6156	2083.007		
33	3	CDWX	B30	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	9.4E+07	9E+07	479.32	479.32	0.3755	0.36	49680	71007	21327.3	1475.11	891.9061		
34	3	CDWX	B12	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	1.3E+08	1.9E+08	744.83	1091.9	0.5835	0.49	67620	115354	47734	659.0709	1996.234		
35	3	CDWX	B3	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	7.5E+07	6.6E+07	395.35	343.77	0.3097	0.36	49680	58767	9087.43	3461.935	380.036		
36	3	CDWX	B4	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	1.3E+08	1.1E+08	690.75	624.39	0.5411	0.49	67620	94239	26619.1	1181.862	1113.21		
37	3	CDWX	B13	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	3.4E+07	7.8E+07	175.74	410.83	0.1377	0.29	40020	32770	-7249.8	-4339.45	-303.186		
38	3	CDWX	B5	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	9.1E+07	7.8E+07	483.18	410.83	0.3785	0.36	49680	67384	17704.1	1776.994	740.3853		
39	3	CDWX	B14	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	8.4E+07	1.1E+08	442.65	604.49	0.3468	0.36	49680	73557	23876.7	1317.609	998.5211		
40	3	CDWX	B6	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	3.8E+07	3.3E+07	195.46	167.67	0.1531	0.29	40020	173981	133961	234.8447	5602.255		
41	3	CDWX	B15	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	3.9E+07	3.6E+07	201.22	183.11	0.1576	0.29	40020	87245	47225.2	666.172	1974.955		
42	3	CDWX	B45	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	2.8E+08	4.3E+08	1838.3	183.11	1.4401	0.7	96600	181910	85309.6	368.7756	3567.644		
43	3	CDWX	B50	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	3.9E+07	8E+07	201.19	422.9	0.1576	0.29	40020	45414	5393.85	5832.586	225.5706		
44	3	CDWX	B58	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	3619714	8626511	18.116	43.316	0.0142	0.29	40020	13860	-26160	-1202.61	0		
45	3	CDWX	B52	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	5E+07	0	259.28	0	0.2031	0.29	40020	35052	-4968.3	-6332.15	0		
46	3	CDWX	B1	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	1.1E+08	8.2E+07	617.02	434.35	0.4834	0.36	49680	45414	-4266.2	-7374.35	0		

26259 46145

88903.17

Table 4.1 : Steel Quantity Estimation of G + 20 fixed base

S.No		storey	Load Combination	beam id	beam (mm)	Steel quantity estimation of G+ 20 with SSI										Shear resistance of section					
						Section Properties(mm)				Material properties(N/mm ²)		Moment(Nmm)		Ast(mm ²)		P%	I	N/mm ²	Vmax (N)	Vs (N)	spacing mm
length	b(m)	D	cover	d	fck	fy	Sagging	Hogging	bottom	top	bottom	top	resistance of section								
1	3	CDWX	B17	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	91073327	3.13E+08	485.359	2178	0.3802	0.36	49680	123988	74308	423.3721	3107.574
2	3	CDWX	B18	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	1.54E+08	2.97E+08	863.459	2009	0.6764	0.49	67620	188154	120534	261.0054	5040.738
3	3	CDWX	B19	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	1.78E+08	2.64E+08	1028.87	1685	0.806	0.57	78660	142983	64323	489.0962	2689.982
4	3	CDWX	B20	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	93005045	2.84E+08	496.415	1873	0.3889	0.36	49680	114675	64995	484.0383	2718.091
5	3	CDWX	B21	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	74861591	41820860	393.963	214.8	0.3086	0.36	49680	51690.8	2010.8	15645.25	84.09326
6	3	CDWX	B22	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	70578581	2.06E+08	370.219	1226	0.29	0.36	49680	96323.5	46644	674.4794	1950.63
7	3	CDWX	B23	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	1.85E+08	1.83E+08	1076.59	1057	0.8434	0.57	78660	113641	34981	899.339	1462.919
8	3	CDWX	B24	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	1.24E+08	2.12E+08	679.674	1269	0.5325	0.49	67620	128247	60627	518.9097	2535.432
9	3	CDWX	B25	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	1.08E+08	1.54E+08	580.982	868.7	0.4551	0.36	49680	134936	85256	369.0078	3565.399
10	3	CDWX	B26	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	1.57E+08	1.57E+08	886.734	886.7	0.6947	0.49	67620	68703.2	1083.2	29043.93	45.29897
11	3	CDWX	B27	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	1.13E+08	1.49E+08	837.583	837.6	0.6562	0.49	67620	104493	36873	853.2115	1542.009
12	3	CDWX	B28	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	45266476	1.36E+08	233.078	754.3	0.1826	0.29	40020	69477.8	29458	1067.973	1231.923
13	3	CDWX	B29	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	84281198	2.77E+08	446.768	1810	0.35	0.36	49680	122095	72415	434.4421	3028.39
14	3	CDWX	B51	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	1.33E+08	2.73E+08	735.247	1775	0.576	0.49	0.36	119353	119352	263.5898	4991.316
15	3	CDWX	B31	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	1.22E+08	1.9E+08	668.663	1109	0.5238	0.49	67620	123037	55417	567.6969	2317.54
16	3	CDWX	B32	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	87014291	1.92E+08	462.244	1122	0.3621	0.36	49680	104999	55319	568.7007	2313.449
17	3	CDWX	B33	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	87113044	1.97E+08	462.804	1157	0.3626	0.36	49680	151348	101668	309.4385	4251.766
18	3	CDWX	B34	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	98711084	1.68E+08	525.29	960.5	0.4146	0.36	49680	103496	53816	584.5844	2250.59
19	3	CDWX	B35	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	95280312	77365259	509.485	407.9	0.3991	0.36	49680	67492.2	17812	1766.21	744.9056
20	3	CDWX	B42	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	82366474	3.67E+08	435.968	3014	0.3415	0.36	49680	114693	65013	483.904	2718.845
21	3	CDWX	B60	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	99697538	2.34E+08	535.007	1436	0.4191	0.36	49680	136129	86449	363.9145	3615.3
22	3	CDWX	B54	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	9.3E+07	2.3E+08	1437.6	1438	1.126	0.64	88320	135605	47285	665.33	1977.45
23	3	CDWX	B36	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	87387341	2.24E+08	464.362	1355	0.3638	0.36	49680	102878	53198	591.382	2224.721
24	3	CDWX	B37	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	81640954	2.52E+08	431.885	1587	0.3383	0.36	49680	107143	57463	547.482	2403.111
25	3	CDWX	B38	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	83325675	2.57E+08	441.374	1632	0.3458	0.36	49680	108376	58696	535.9863	2454.652
26	3	CDWX	B39	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	83486087	3.3E+08	442.279	2389	0.3465	0.36	49680	120706	71026	442.9386	2970.299
27	3	CDWX	B40	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	3.42E+08	3.42E+08	2557	2557	2.0031	0.82	113160	81732.3	-31428	-1001.03	0
28	3	CDWX	B10	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	1.02E+08	1.01E+08	548.504	544.8	0.4297	0.36	49680	80544	30864	1019.313	1290.732
29	3	CDWX	B9	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	1.11E+08	79981760	600.436	422.6	0.4704	0.36	49680	45352.5	-4327.5	-7269.87	0
30	3	CDWX	B8	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	1.11E+08	1.01E+08	600.436	543.7	0.4704	0.36	49680	82500.4	32820	958.553	1372.548
31	3	CDWX	B2	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	1.62E+08	1.41E+08	918.483	786.4	0.7195	0.49	67620	110934	43314	726.326	1811.39
32	3	CDWX	B11	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	1.33E+08	1.97E+08	731.398	1161	0.573	0.49	67620	116945	49325	637.8088	2062.781
33	3	CDWX	B30	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	94348688	90656686	482.979	483	0.3784	0.36	49680	71225.6	21546	1460.161	901.0375
34	3	CDWX	B12	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	1.35E+08	1.86E+08	746.516	1083	0.5848	0.49	67620	115109	47489	662.4663	1986.003
35	3	CDWX	B3	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	75347219	66187182	396.666	346	0.3107	0.36	49680	58909.8	9229.8	3408.52	385.9916
36	3	CDWX	B4	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	1.26E+08	1.15E+08	690.997	623.6	0.5413	0.49	67620	94218.1	26598	1182.795	1112.332
37	3	CDWX	B13	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	94348894	36760105	176.921	188.1	0.1386	0.29	40020	32551.3	-7468.7	-4212.24	0
38	3	CDWX	B5	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	91450056	74940515	487.512	394.4	0.3819	0.36	49680	66875.9	17196	1829.512	719.1316
39	3	CDWX	B14	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	83465724	1.11E+08	442.164	602.8	0.3464	0.36	49680	73471.4	23791	1322.332	994.9547
40	3	CDWX	B6	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	38298123	33199019	196.228	169.5	0.1537	0.29	40020	174048	134028	234.7272	5605.06
41	3	CDWX	B15	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	39490619	36310474	202.507	185.8	0.1586	0.29	40020	87135.4	47115	667.7247	1970.363
42	3	CDWX	B45	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	2.79E+08	4.28E+08	1826.55	183.1	1.4309	0.7	96600	181404	84804	370.9762	3546.48
43	3	CDWX	B50	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	76001659	76001659	400.311	400.3	0.3136	0.36	49680	43294.2	-6385.8	-4926.59	0
44	3	CDWX	B58	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	3608867	8612348	18.0613	43.24	0.0141	0.29	40020	13846.7	-26173	-1201.99	0
45	3	CDWX	B52	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	50177793	50177793	259.277	259.3	0.2031	0.29	40020	35051.7	-4968.3	-6332.15	0
46	3	CDWX	B1	8380	230	600	45	555	25	415	1.14E+08	81129608	618.187	429	0.4843	0.36	49680	174894	125214	251.2509	0

28837.1 47456

87995.23

Table 4.2 : Steel Quantity Estimation of G + 20 SSI

Observations:

- 1) It is observed that the analysis results of shear and moments increase for the SSI case with respect to the fixed base case.
- 2) The changed steel quantity calculation indicates an early set of yielding and cracks of the structure thus affecting its serviceability.
- 3) The SSI affects the shear forces with increased shear values observed with respect to the fixed base. The percentage steel which influences the shear strength of the section is also found to be on the lesser side of the required thus affecting its serviceability.

G+30		Moments		
S.No.	Beam Id	ADLWX	ADLSXP	% variation
1	B17	284.344	109.37	61.53602678
2	B67	426.854	169.56	60.27681596
3	B68	148.13	67.97	54.11462904
4	B19	37.083	8.57	76.88967991
5	B20	260.659	118.48	54.54597769
6	B69	194.022	106.38	45.17116616
7	B70	182.1	105.32	42.16364635
8	B71	510.29	232.34	54.46902742

G+50		Moments			Floor No:15
S.No.	Beam Id	ADLWX	ADLSXP	% variation	
1	B17	334.015	94.37	71.74677784	
2	B18	1151.846	399.35	65.32956663	
4	B19	229.458	8.35	96.36098981	
5	B20	435.957	207.76	52.34392383	
6	B21	137.547	120.78	12.19001505	
7	B22	331.056	122.56	62.97907303	
8	B23	403.057	416.92	-3.439463897	

Table 4.3 : Comparison of wind loads and earthquake loads in G + 30, G + 50

The above table shows the values of moments due lateral forces for G+30 and G+50 high-risers. It is observed that the moments due to wind far exceed the moment due to earthquake forces.

The reduced stiffness on account of the SSI increases the corresponding results of analysis. The earthquake load case results for G+20 were found to decrease due to the consideration of the soil structure interaction effects in the previous sections. The above table shows that the load case wind load causes lateral forces which are found to be greater than the earthquake , thus the above result related to earthquake load case is of no significance for multi – risers, but it can be seen that there could be considerable saving of steel due to consideration of SSI on low rise buildings.

G+50

Comparison of earthquake lateral forces of fixed model and SSI model			
STOREY	FIXED	SSI	% change
1	4225.69	4225.54	-0.00355
2	4203.21	4203.17	-0.00095
3	4141.61	4141.61	0
4	4067.4	4067.38	-0.00049
5	4011.3	4011.26	-0.001
6	3962.57	3962.54	-0.00076
7	3893.7	3893.69	-0.00026
8	3799.73	3799.74	0.000263
9	3698.8	3698.8	0
10	3596.31	3596.32	0.000278
11	3336.93	3336.38	-0.01648
12	3336.93	3336.99	0.001798
13	3187.42	3187.53	0.003451
14	3035.75	3035.81	0.001976
15	2872.26	2872.33	0.002437
16	2689.86	2689.95	0.003346
17	2499.91	2500	0.0036
18	2313.96	2314.05	0.003889
19	2119.59	2119.69	0.004718
20	1908.2	1908.32	0.006289
21	1691.34	1691.45	0.006504
22	1502.61	1502.69	0.005324
23	1315.59	1315.69	0.007601
24	1055.46	1055.63	0.016107
25	684.87	685.09	0.032123
26	288.14	288.2	0.020823
27	364.85	364.61	-0.06578
28	683.95	683.77	-0.02632
29	909.25	909.16	-0.0099
30	1077.98	1077.89	-0.00835
31	1255.72	1255.61	-0.00876
32	1462.33	1462.21	-0.00821
33	1662.5	1662.4	-0.00602
34	1841.65	1841.56	-0.00489
35	2015.82	2015.72	-0.00496
36	2194.64	2194.54	-0.00456
37	2366.35	2366.26	-0.0038
38	2519.97	2519.88	-0.00357
39	2663.09	2663	-0.00338
40	2805.88	2805.79	-0.00321
41	2940.17	2940.08	-0.00306
42	3054.19	3054.11	-0.00262
43	3154.97	3154.87	-0.00317
44	3254.93	3254.89	-0.00123
45	3347.91	3347.84	-0.00209
46	341.51	3418.44	900.978
47	3470.04	3469.97	-0.00202
48	3526.53	3526.46	-0.00198
49	3597.25	3597.18	-0.00195
50	3651.52	3651.46	-0.00164

Table 4.4 Comparison of earthquake response spectrum of fixed base versus SSI

The analysis of wind loads is done by the application of the static wind load forces in the form of pressure calculated from the IS Code provisions. Thus it can be observed that there is a uniform increase in the analysis results for the earthquake load case.

The comparison of earthquake lateral forces in the previous table shows that there is a non-uniform variation in the lateral forces which could be accounted for due to the response spectrum analysis method which considers the natural frequencies of motion of the structure and also the mass matrix to arrive at the shape factors for the lateral forces at various storeys.

Comparison of design of G+20 at fixed location

storey	beam id	(mm)				Moment (Mu) (Nmm)		N/mm2		(mm)		Ast (mm2)		Ptc		Change in steel Ptc	V (N)		Avg Shear Stress(N/mm2)		change in average stressPtc
		Depth	Location	cover		Fixed	SSI	fck	fy	b	d	Fixed	SSI	Fixed	SSI		Fixed	SSI	Fixed	SSI	
1	B17	600	5000	45	3847000000	3847000000	25	415	230	555	12153.345	12153.3453	9.521	9.52	0	2876918.62	2486218.45	22.53755284	19.47683862	-13.58050823	
2	B17	600	5000	45	4039000000	3690000000	25	415	230	555	12452.934	11902.7669	9.756	9.32	-4.417968562	3308592.7	2751289.92	25.91925343	21.55338754	-16.84410354	
3	B17	600	5000	45	4051000000	3666000000	25	415	230	555	12471.419	11863.9956	9.77	9.29	-4.870523083	3390131.2	2783121.32	26.55801958	21.80275221	-17.9052032	
4	B17	600	5000	45	3934000000	3465000000	25	415	230	555	12290.001	11534.1705	9.628	9.04	-6.149964403	3350291.9	2746489.99	26.24592166	21.51578527	-18.02236725	
5	B17	600	5000	45	3752000000	3308000000	25	415	230	555	12002.347	11269.8334	9.403	8.83	-6.103082425	3283945.8	2710030.58	25.72617156	21.23016514	-17.47639136	
6	B17	600	5000	45	3508000000	3164000000	25	415	230	555	11605.518	11021.8116	9.092	8.63	-5.029561102	3214767.1	2690181.45	25.1842311	21.07466863	-16.31799859	
7	B17	600	5000	45	3205000000	2899000000	25	415	230	555	11092.994	10550.1553	8.69	8.26	-4.893523829	3152351.8	2695058.45	24.69527458	21.11287466	-14.50641867	
8	B17	600	5000	45	2833000000	2575000000	25	415	230	555	10429.369	9943.13561	8.17	7.79	-4.662155342	3101707.8	2727791.72	24.29853349	21.3693045	-12.0551678	
9	B17	600	5000	45	2405000000	2207000000	25	415	230	555	9609.3118	9205.25688	7.528	7.21	-4.204826965	3054689.62	2784150.91	23.93019679	21.81081794	-8.856504053	
10	B17	600	5000	45	1701000000	1581000000	25	415	230	555	8081.4056	7791.13412	6.331	6.1	-3.591843562	1677987.42	2851793.37	13.14522068	22.34072362	69.95320322	
11	B17	600	5000	45	2345000000	2326000000	25	415	230	555	9488.6881	9450.16956	7.433	7.4	-0.405941212	2011635.64	1662543.54	15.75899444	13.02423455	-17.35364462	
12	B17	600	5000	45	2298000000	2231000000	25	415	230	555	9393.1176	9255.17278	7.358	7.25	-1.468572914	2331744.133	1944726.15	18.26669904	15.23483079	-16.59778951	
13	B17	600	5000	45	2290000000	2181000000	25	415	230	555	9376.7532	9150.87406	7.368	7.17	-2.408927318	2642915.77	2208826.08	20.70439303	17.30376874	-16.42465095	
14	B17	600	5000	45	2237000000	2091000000	25	415	230	555	9267.6098	8960.07742	7.26	7.02	-3.318356511	3858164.7	2470340.2	30.22455699	19.35244967	-35.97110564	
15	B17	600	5000	45	2153000000	1976000000	25	415	230	555	9091.9442	8710.20178	7.123	6.82	-1.198688347	3562414.8	2734553.02	27.90767568	21.42227199	-23.23878118	
16	B17	600	5000	45	2032000000	1439000000	25	415	230	555	8832.7634	7433.01729	6.92	5.82	-15.84720496	3249566	3004657.8	25.45684293	23.53825147	-7.536643355	
17	B17	600	5000	45	1895000000	1666000000	25	415	230	555	8529.8099	8005.02908	6.682	6.27	-6.152315624	3562414.8	3290498.2	27.90767568	25.7750255	-7.632929214	
18	B17	600	5000	45	1663000000	1439000000	25	415	230	555	7990.6272	7433.01729	6.26	5.82	-6.978299947	3858164.7	3571111.1	30.22455699	27.9758018	-7.440159307	
19	B17	600	5000	45	1673000000	1356000000	25	415	230	555	8014.6159	7215.46942	6.279	5.65	-9.971114418	4284647.7	3955642.2	33.56559107	30.98818801	-7.678706	
20	B17	600	5000	45	814200000	694700000	25	415	230	555	5591.1391	5164.56081	4.38	4.05	-7.629541271	3884107.6	3748091.8	30.42779162	29.3622546	-3.501854583	

197765.71 188013.195 total

Table 4.5 : Comparison of design of G +20 at fixed location

The table shows the variation of shear and moment values for the G+20 building at fixed location at a span of 5m from one of the ends for the cases of fixed base and SSI model. This shows the changed detailing requirements on account of consideration of the flexibility of the base.

Chapter 5

Conclusion

5.1 Introduction

In this study, the soil-structure –interaction comparison of 10, 20 and 50 storeyed buildings are done with the respective fixed base models using the softwares Etaabs, SAFE and MS Excel. Response Spectrum analysis and wind load analysis are carried out to do performance comparison. Based on the observations some conclusions are drawn which are presented in this chapter.

5.2 Conclusions

- The wind load forces are more predominant than earthquake forces as the height of the structure increases. For all the buildings considered the wind load forces were greater than the earthquake forces.
- The reduced stiffness at the base caused increased values of forces (moment and shear).
- For the multi risers which usually have a raft foundation on hard strata it is assumed that the fixed base is a conservative approach. But the modified stiffness matrix affects the wind load forces (shears and moments).
- On comparing the envelope case for the SSI case and the fixed model of the multi-riser an increased moment and subsequently higher amount of steel was found to be required. Also, there was difference in the shear, moment diagrams across the flexural member with change in contraflexure points and increased forces resulting in changed detailing requirements. Thus, it affects the performance and serviceability of structure
- The wind effects are dominant for the multi-risers. On the comparison of earthquake forces considerable difference was seen in the earthquake forces between SSI and fixed base case. There was an increase in moments and hence steel requirement and a varied change in S.F.D and B.M.D showed a requirement of change in detailing.

5.3 Scope for future works

The present study involves the comparison of the moments and shears for the cases of fixed base and SSI case of multi riser and the variation in design due to the changes. Future work can be done on the following topics:

- There is ample scope for study and betterment of the soil structure using continuum and finite element models.
- The small-scale models can be prepared and compared with the largely conservative fixed base model to study the change in deformation pattern and further validate the effect of SSI on the design of structure.
- The change in earthquakes forces due to SSI is considerable hence requiring extensive study in low-rise buildings.

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